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“Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Student”

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Abstract

This research study aims to determine the impact of inclusive education on the student's motivation to learn, together with its relationship to the academic performance of the students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School. The result of the study can help the teachers improve their skills in teaching their students, in promoting inclusivity in the classroom and can help students improve their academic performance through motivation and a sense of belongingness. Workshops, peer tutoring program, extracurricular activities, and other activities can be proposed that will help teachers to enhance and develop their skills in teaching the students and promoting inclusivity in the classroom and to motivate students to improve their academic performance. The respondents of the study are the selected senior high school students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024. The researchers were able to enumerate the Grade 11 respondents (155) and Grade 12 respondents (156) with a total of three hundred eleven (311).

The researchers used a self-made survey questionnaire to determine the relationship between inclusive education, students' motivation and academic performance of selected senior high school students of Sto. Tomas Senior High School. The researchers created 41 sets of questions to identify the relationship. The first question is about the proficiency level of the senior high school students. The 20 sets of questions determine students' evaluation of Inclusive Education, and the level of Students' Motivation also has 20 sets of questions.

To analyze and interpret the data gathered, the researchers used mean and Pearson's r correlation as a statistical tool.

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that there is a significant relationship between inclusive education, students' motivation and academic performance of the selected senior high school students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School. Furthermore, Workshops, peer tutoring program, extracurricular activities will improve the educational performance of the students.

Moreover, it is recommended for schools to create environments where all students feel valued, supported, and empowered to learn and thrive. Teachers should assess the individual strengths, weaknesses, learning styles, and preferences of each student. This could involve pre-assessments, observations, discussions with students, and input from parents or previous teachers: teachers can adapt their teaching methods, materials, and assessments to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities, and catering the different learning preferences, and establishing a positive and inclusive classroom culture where diversity is celebrated, and respect is valued that are essential for motivating students. Students may demonstrate respect and acceptance towards their peers, regardless of differences in abilities, backgrounds, or identities, students may also educate their peers and teachers about the importance on inclusivity and diversity. Parents may also support and promote inclusive education; they may collaborate with teachers and school administrators to ensure that their child's individual needs and strengths are recognized and addressed. Future researchers can explore the intersection of inclusive education and student motivation and its role in advancing educational practices and policies, they can deepen the understanding of the complex dynamics at play and contribute valuable insights to the field.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Motivation, Academic Performance

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Introduction

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The inclusive education approach is a tool used by the teacher in teaching the students, it provides a good quality of education to all kinds of students in one classroom. In this educational approach, every student in the classroom, with or without any special needs, will acquire the quality of education that a learner needs in learning. A teacher in this approach disregards the different physical capabilities of a learner but acknowledges the different characteristics and abilities if the students are willing to learn.

In the amendment to DepEd Order No. 022, Series of 2023 a new DepEd Order No. 003, Series of 2024 has been released, which is articulated to the MATATAG Agenda that aims to "Take good care of learners by promoting learner well-being, inclusive education and positive learning environment". This memorandum aims to provide an inclusive education and a positive learning environment to foster all kinds of learners in the classroom, as this main priority is the students and teacher health and safety.

Inclusive education is an educational approach in which all students are equal, take the same classes, and contribute to and participate in all kinds of activities inside or outside the classroom. It ensures access to quality education for the learners, even if the learners have different beliefs, backgrounds, and abilities (IEC, 2020). The concept of inclusive education is that the students with

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special needs will be placed in a regular classroom with other students who do not have any special requirements.

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It implies that learners with or without disabilities will participate and learn together in the same classes (Kanchiuniv.ac.in, 2017). To effectively implement inclusive education, students should be motivated to learn in a wide range of diversity in the classroom.

On the other hand, motivation is one of the best strategies for effective teaching and learning; it helps the students to focus on the goals, and it enables the students to maintain attention for an extended period (Hawthorne, 2021). Moreover, motivation has a significant role in the success and achievement of a student; the higher the level of motivation the students have, the higher of learning outcomes are achieved (Wardani et al., 2020). In addition, the higher the students achieve the learning outcomes, the higher the learner's academic performance. Academic performance is commonly defined as the student's grades in a subject or the Grade Point Average (GPA); however, there are many factors affecting student performance (Williams, 2018). Some of the factors affecting the student's academic performance are socioeconomic factors, parental background, peers, teacher's effectiveness, and facilities at school (eQourse, 2022).

Inclusive education is essential because it gives the quality of education that the students need without experiencing any discrimination. Since the school

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provides the first relationship of the children to the outside world, letting a child to develop socializing and interacting skills (OSF, 2019); on the other hand, motivation is important because it shows the willingness and interest of the students in learning. The more focus and effort that a student put into work, the easier it will be to achieve the academic objectives. A motivated learner will produce positive outcomes, show a more extraordinary passion for moving forward on training stage, and accomplish progressively challenging objectives (SIC, 2023). Hence, both inclusive education and motivation took part in improving students' performance (IPL, 2023).

Hence, the students' evaluation of inclusive education can be divided into four terms: the learning environment, social environment, physical environment, and ethnic diversity. The learning environment is the surroundings in which students learn and are constantly changing and growing as learners (WGU, 2021). The social environment is the human social habitat, which includes the nearby physical setting, interpersonal connections, and cultural contexts in which a group of people live and interact (LI, 2023). The physical environment describes the general structure and arrangement of a specific classroom and its learning stations (IC, 2023). Ethnic diversity is the influence of ethnic and cultural variety on identity in significance to the self-perception that affects the thoughts, feelings, and actions of an individual (Skidmore, 2021). By identifying the evaluation of the

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students in the terms mentioned above, a teacher may have a strategy for approaching inclusive education in the classroom.

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Additionally, the level of student motivations is examined in different terms, which is the intrinsic, extrinsic, affective, and expectancy. Intrinsic motivation is engaging in a particular activity for its own sake and not for some reward because the activity itself is rewarding, while extrinsic motivation is doing an activity and accomplishing a task to have a reward or avoid punishment (Cherry, 2022).

On the other hand, the emotions connected to a particular situation or interest, as well as motivation to do a task or subject matter, are examples of affective motivation; this can be a value associated with or attributed to a subject or study, the enjoyment experienced, or the intrinsic incentive to engage in this task (Lockl et al., 2021). According to Juneja (2015), an individual's inclination to act in a certain way is influenced by the strength of expectations in a specific outcome, as well as how motivating such outcomes are to the learners. In determining the level of students' motivation in different terms, it will be helpful in inclusive education to motivate students.

The purpose of this study is to determine the impact of inclusive education on the student's motivation to learn, together with its relationship to the academic performance of the students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School. Moreover, it aims to determine the influence of using inclusive education and students' motivation

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on the academic performance of the learners to recommend the school further to utilize inclusive education and students' motivation effectively.

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Theoretical Framework

According to the **Contact Theory** by Allport, contact with all members of a group can reduce conflict and arguments; thus, it helps the group to have a good relationship, create a positive attitude, and gain a proper understanding of the different individuals within a group. Allport's theory has four conditions to be met in reducing conflict and creating a good relationship with all the members. The four conditions are equal status between groups, having common goals, two different groups working cooperatively, and support from the authorities or institution (Mcleod, 2023).

This theory is anchored to the study because it connects to an inclusive education approach in teaching and learning, as this theory can strengthen the relationship between the students and the teachers. When the teacher treats each student equally without discrimination and without looking at the different characteristics of every student's, it can create a good relationship with the students, making the learners share goals with everyone, which is to pass the quarter or gain knowledge through learning from the different characteristics of every student and through sharing ideas. Upon building this kind of connection, it

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will have unity in the class, and the student may have the motivation to be present in class and do the schoolwork more comfortably with every learner in the class.

Moreover, proper guidance from the teacher in charge is one of the factors needed in creating this kind of connection since the teachers are the one who has the authority to build the any kind of classroom management.

Also, better contact between students and teachers can be an excellent way to give a quality education to all.

On the other hand, McClelland's Theory of Needs, or the Achievement Motivation Theory, states that human behaviors are affected by the three needs of power, affiliation, and achievement. Power motivation is the desire to influence other people, wanting to lead, control, and tend to improve the self-esteem of a learner. Affiliation as a motivation is socializing or interacting with other people, wanting to be supported by an individual, making to do work in a group, and sharing ideas. Achievement in motivation is the motivation to excel and accomplish something and the urge to accept struggles to be able to achieve success willingly (Juneja, 2015).

Suppose students acquire power, affiliation, and achievement. In that case, it can be a valuable tool to motivate a learner to achieve his goal in a class and have a desire to create more achievements. Through collaborating with the other

learners, it can build a good relationship and, at the same time, make the activities successful through the collaboration of ideas.

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Conceptual Framework

The figure below shows the paradigm of the independent study and the relationship of the dependent Variables model that fits the ideas of the researchers.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm

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Figure 1, the Research Paradigm of the study, presents the inclusive education, student motivation, and academic performance of the selected senior high school students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School AY 2023-2024.

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The first box is the independent variables that present students' evaluation of inclusive education in terms of learning environment, social environment, physical environment, and ethnic diversity, and the level of students' motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, affective, and expectancy.

The last box is the dependent variables that present the Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to determine the relationship between inclusive education, students' motivation, and academic performance of the selected Senior High School students at the Sto. Tomas Senior High School and the researchers want to:

1. Determine the Learners' Proficiency Level of the selected Senior High School students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School.

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2. Determine how the Senior High School students evaluate inclusive education in terms of the learning environment, social environment, physical environment, and ethnic diversity.
3. Determine the students' level of motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, affective, and expectancy.
4. Determine the significant relationship between inclusive education and students' Learner Proficiency Level.
5. Determine the significant relationship between the students' motivation and students' Learner Proficiency Level.
6. Determine the significant relationship between inclusive education and the student's motivation.
7. Develop an action plan for teachers to use inclusive education in teaching to motivate the students and improve academic performance.

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Statement of the Problem

This study generally aims to determine the relationship between inclusive education, student motivation, and academic performance of the selected Senior High School students. Specifically, it will seek to answer the following:

1. What is the Learners' Proficiency Level of the selected Senior High School students at the Sto. Tomas Senior High School?
2. What is the student's evaluation of inclusive education in terms of:

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- 2.1 learning environment;
- 2.2 social environment;
- 2.3 physical environment, and
- 2.4 ethnic diversity?

3. What is the level of students' motivation in terms of;

- 3.1 intrinsic motivation;
- 3.2 extrinsic motivation;
- 3.3 affective motivational aspect;
- 3.4 expectancy theory of motivation?

4. Is there a significant relationship between inclusive education and students' Learner Proficiency Level?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' motivation and students' Learner Proficiency Level?

6. Is there a significant relationship between inclusive education and the student's motivation?

7. Based on the study, what action plan can be proposed to promote inclusive education and enhance students' motivation and academic performance?

Hypotheses

There was a significant relationship between the students' evaluation of inclusive education and students' academic performance.

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There was a significant relationship between the students' motivation and students' academic performance.

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There was a significant relationship between the student's evaluation of inclusive education and motivation.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This study's review of related literature focuses on the Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation, and Academic Performance of the selected Senior High School students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School. Through relevant study materials, including journals, articles, research, and the Internet, it will present the situation and its variables. Every resource will help the researchers gain a more thorough comprehension of the framework and methodology of the study.

According to Kafia et al. (2023), inclusive education should be seen as a medical psycho-pedagogy that promotes social inclusion and healthy personalities rather than rejecting differences and attempting to provide everyone with the best chances for individual and group development. The evidence-based approach's theoretical perspective is much more expansive than the traditional definition of inclusion. It acknowledges that there is an inherent risk of exclusion associated with inclusive education, which must be actively prevented. Additionally, it emphasizes the significance of involving all stakeholders in the

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creation of a genuinely welcoming community that is sensitive to the full range of differences present in children's lives.

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Additionally, in the article by Kart and Kart (2021), in many countries, inclusive education is displacing traditional teaching approaches. By inclusive education, students with disabilities receive instruction in general education classrooms alongside students without disabilities. If inclusive education is to become increasingly popular, research must look at the effects of inclusion for both kids with special needs and students who are developing typically. However, a larger body of research has been done on the impact of including disabled students in inclusive settings than on the same results for students without impairments. Research indicates that students with disabilities have both social and academic benefits; however, the effects of inclusion on general education students are not as well known. Research indicates that the impact of different educational attainment levels on the academic performance of students without impairments changes and that inclusion has different effects on these people.

Furthermore, according to the article by Choi (2021), in urban elementary and elementary/middle schools, it has been demonstrated that the school-wide applications model (SAM) has the potential to be a successful model for inclusive school-wide change that will increase equity-based inclusive education practices and improve student achievement for all kids. Since inclusive education serves

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students with a variety of learning requirements and cultural backgrounds in addition to those with impairments, schools must comprehend how inclusive education enhances an institution.

Additionally, in the article by Fitri (2022), it is widely believed that providing inclusive education to children with special needs is essential to facilitating more accessible social environment adaptation. A curriculum modification process that integrates local content, the attributes of children with special needs, and the national education curriculum can be used to create a humanistic inclusion education curriculum. An educational establishment that has effectively implemented inclusive education has enhanced students' academic and social competencies in a humanistic way.

The researchers agree with Dalgaard et al. (2022) observation that there is a lack of educational theories that explain how inclusive education can benefit students with special educational needs (SEN). It is surprising, given the growing global trend towards inclusive education for SEN students. The proponents of inclusive education argue that separating SEN children from peers can lead to social exclusion and stigmatization, which can adversely affect the learner's confidence and self-concept. Additionally, the composition of the groups in which SEN students are taught plays a crucial role in the learner's overall well-being, socio-emotional growth, and academic success.

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In addition, Steigmann (2020) said that despite being a globally acknowledged human right, inclusive education for people with disabilities is still far from being correctly and ultimately implemented. Given that this fundamental human right is applicable to all people, including refugees, its non-implementation affects everyone as well. As a result, the study describes that children with disabilities have the right to inclusive education, as well as the barriers and difficulties faced in obtaining it.

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Hence, according to Martynchuk (2016), due to the coordination of the social and educational integration of individuals with special needs and the shared desire for social justice around the world, it focuses on the necessity of reviewing inclusive education as a crucial component of educational research; it is stated that the development of inclusive education requires both professionals with established competence in the field of inclusive education and a new academic lot that will serve the needs.

Zahid et al. (2023) state that behavioral problems are present in children with disorders. Behavioral problems may be a result of long-term conditions or transient stressful events in an individual's life. Children with special needs who have behavioral disorders may exhibit traits like an incapacity to learn that cannot be attributed to cerebral, medical, or sensory issues. When children are raised in an environment that are safe, loved, and supported, are more likely to thrive

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academically. A welcoming environment can have a significant impact on the child's behavior, motivation, and overall success in school. The cross-sectional survey has been conducted to ascertain how children in inclusive education are affected academically by behavioral problems. Thus, the study shows that children in the special needs group and those in the general population differed significantly in terms of structured activities, school routine skills, and overall behavioral checklist. Some of the children in the mainstream group had no trouble at all with the structured activity, whereas most of the children with special needs had difficulty. Most of the mainstream students completed the school routine skills, and only a few of the children with special needs were able to finish during school hours. According to the behavior checklist, most children with special needs showed behavioral concerns, compared to most mainstream children who showed no behavioral issues. The study concludes that a correlation exists between the participants' general behavior in both groups during the structured activity and the academic schedules.

Additionally, in the article by Tainá et al. (2020) states that the primary goal of inclusive education is to examine the instructional strategies. It was evident that the inclusive education topic exists in the educational environment of today, and the educators and experts participating in the school's pedagogical organization must possess a consistently more perceptive glance in that direction was

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observed upon data analysis that awareness of various forms of disability and disorders is incredibly beneficial to educators. Based on the understanding of certain infirmities, an educator can create a work schedule that will meet the individual student's needs.

Moreover, in the article of Mendoza and Heymann (2022), a review is concentrated on interventions in low- and lower-middle-income nations that addressed the implementation of inclusive education. Research showed that in as little as 10 hours, teacher training can have a favorable impact on teachers' attitudes toward inclusion, the awareness of disability, and teaching practices. Second, highly positive assessments demonstrated that incorporating individual and small group instruction into inclusive ample group instruction enhanced results in contexts with limited resources. Third, there is evidence of a favorable correlation between inclusive practice, academic success, and facilities that are easily accessible. Lastly, with quantifiable good outcomes for inclusion, interventions for creating action items for International Education (IE) can involve many groups of government employees, community people, teachers, and parents.

On the other hand, Trujillo and Tanner (2014) mention that students receive an inclusive education because it incorporates structure into the layout of courses and classrooms. Students with varying backgrounds, abilities, and life

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experiences can all succeed in this structure. Building a sense of belonging on campus is crucial for fostering academic success, and it is a message that is conveyed to students through pedagogical decisions: "You belong here, and you deserve to be here."

In the study of Eke (2021), children receiving instruction in an inclusive classroom outperformed those receiving education in a unique class in terms of academic achievement increases. Based on the findings, a few recommendations were made, such as the following: lecturers and other relevant staff in higher education institutions should collaborate to create an inclusive environment in the classroom; applicable commissions for tertiary institutions should make suitable laws that will prompt tertiary institutions to adapt inclusive classroom and inclusive education practices.

Additionally, the study of Szumski et al. (2017) shows that the inclusive classroom environment positively affects the academic achievement of students without special educational needs (SEN). The study also emphasizes that inclusive education is associated with the academic achievement of the students.

Hence, the study by Golland (2019) found that when inclusive education is used in teaching or co-taught, it could affect the academic motivation of the students and the student's engagement in learning. Moreover, co-taught

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classrooms that are inclusive have a positive impact on academic motivation and engagement among students with disabilities.

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The study by Li and Singh (2022), entitled "Inclusive Learning Environment Can Improve Student Learning and Motivation Beliefs," said that students' perception of the inclusiveness of the learning environment significantly impacts the motivational beliefs and performance in the course. Perceived recognition and sense of belonging are critical factors in predicting overall physics identity and self-efficacy, respectively. While peer interaction has a more minor direct effect, it still plays a crucial role in shaping students' sense of belonging and recognition. Instructors should focus on strategies to enhance students' interactions with peers to improve outcomes.

Moreover, according to the article in UB (2024), said that the learning environment includes the intellectual, social, emotional, and physical environments, all of which will affect learning. Instructor-student interactions and the tone of the course may affect how students approach learning and work through difficulties. The demographics of students within the course and how peers interact also play a vital role in this environment. Furthermore, the study of Opio et al. (2023) mentioned that the inclusion of learners in secondary education has been fundamentally associated with the learning environment. However, little

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is known about the relationships between types of learning environments and inclusion when moderated by self-efficacy and mediated by disability status.

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Hence, Robb's (2020) article mentioned that a low-risk environment has a deep connection to a positive social environment. A positive social environment promotes acceptance, kindness, forgiveness, and the opportunity to experience failure without consequences. This kind of environment helps the students to become acquainted with a healthy learning environment; it gives the students the power to pursue education, build confidence, and grow as learners.

Moreover, the study by Ackah-Jnr and Danso (2018), entitled "Examining the physical environment of Ghanaian inclusive schools: how accessible, suitable and appropriate is such environment for inclusive schools?" mentioned that poor quality of the physical environment is less accessible for the students with special needs and less suitable for any physical activities. Therefore, improving the ventilation system, decorations, good architectural designs, modification of facilities, and physical landscape of schools is a must to promote accessibility for all kinds of students in the school.

In the article of SE (2019) entitled "The Benefits of Inclusion and Diversity in the Classroom," mentioned that diversity in the classroom lets the student value the different perspective and opinions by showing the different perspectives and opinions of every learner. It could give the child an opportunity to think critically

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about beliefs of every one and make an assumption based in own understanding. Moreover, exposure to diversity can change the way of thinking of an individual by promoting creativity, decision making, and problem-solving. Furthermore, to create a culturally responsive learning environment in the classroom, the teacher should create a culturally responsive environment to foster a classroom where all the learners are respectful and understanding of the differences of every student in class.

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In the book cited by Anabel (2018), in higher education, putting inclusive education's tenets into practice can be difficult; before being implemented in higher education, inclusive education is first created for younger pupils. On the other hand, the necessity for higher education to adopt inclusive methods has grown as more students with disabilities successfully finish early schooling.

According to Bernardino et al. (2020), activity initiation and persistence are both boosted by motivation. The study is conducted to determine how motivation affects Grade 11 students' academic performance. The study's findings demonstrated how encouragement fosters students' curiosity and creativity, which turn fuels to the student's desire to learn and engage in class. The results showed that a student's motivation significantly affects the performance. It plays a significant part in encouraging students to keep up hard work. Students who are

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motivated have more tremendous enthusiasm, put forth more effort and energy, and are more relentless in pursuit of the objectives.

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Moreover, in the article of Mehndroo and Vandana (2020), the primary driving force behind everyone's needs, wants, and behaviors is motivation. Motives are what drive a person to act in a particular way or develop a specific moral inclination. A student's motivation is a crucial component of the academic success, readiness, and eagerness to learn. These driven students are curious and driven to understand the value of education. Furthermore, educators and parents can establish a setting where students can learn in arranged and accomplished by motivating and inspiring students to be dedicated. The results of this investigation showed a strong correlation between the following indicators of motivation: academic achievement, job interest, effort inclusion, competitiveness, social power, participation, and social concern. There have been some suggestions made for enhancing motivation.

Furthermore, in the study of Kum (2022), entitled "The Effects of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation on Student Learning Effectiveness (Case Study: International Students of Estonian Entrepreneurship University of Applied Sciences)," the study found that motivation has a significant influence in human behavior, that motivation is a course of action or inspiration used by a person to meet the desired outcome. Hence, motivation is divided into various factors,

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intrinsic and extrinsic. Moreover, intrinsic motivation has a positive impact on the student's learning effectiveness as this greatly influences the student's learning. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation is much more effective in affecting the student's drive to learn and student performance, as learners have much passion if the learners are intrinsically motivated. Additionally, the study also found that the factor that pushes a person to achieve the desired course of action is motivation. Hence, extrinsic motivation has a favorable impact on student learning effectiveness and so as in academic performance.

In addition, according to Oclaret (2021), in "Impact of Academic Intrinsic Motivation Facets on Student's Academic Performance," the study found that intrinsic motivation has a positive impact on academic performance. Students are found to perform well academically and are very interested in learning. Moreover, the study of Khaliq et al. (2023), entitled "Extrinsic Motivation and Student's Academic Achievement: A Correlational Study," found that the motivating factors persistently influence human behavior and accurately show the factors that encourage a person. Moreover, extrinsic motivation has a positive impact on the student's academic success; the presence of attaining rewards such as high grades and praise from peers extrinsically motivated the learners.

On the other hand, according to Teraoka et al. (2020), "Affective Learning in Physical Education: A Systematic Review", said that affective outcomes have

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four themes: motivation, self-concept, emotional response, and resilience that affect the student's engagement in learning. Moreover, effective teaching strategies that include offering students a choice, promoting explicit criticism, placing a strong emphasis on growth, and posing reasonable questions give the students engagement and motivation to study. Affective learning widely influences this factor. Hence, to create an effective teaching strategy, it should acknowledge the factors that affect effective learning as this still influences the student's motivation to learn. Hence, in the study of Capelle et al. (2023) about expectancy entitled "Trajectories in quantity and quality of motivation and study activities among university students as exams approach," said that the expectation and task value beliefs give a complete framework for characterizing a person's overall motivation to pursue an activity, like a study task, and subsequently fuel study behavior.

Hence, in the article of Kusurkar et al. (2013), academic performance is positively impacted by motivation because it leads to a deeper study strategy and more significant study effort. Encouraging students' self-motivation is crucial to achieving a mindset of deep learning, great action, and, ultimately, good performance. A student's motivation level plays a significant role in influencing the performance, as evidenced by the high effort and effective study techniques of a learner.

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The study by Steinmayr et al. (2019) started to determine the distinct ways in which various facets of students' motivation relate to variations in the academic performance. Research showed that, in addition to intelligence and past performance, students' ability self-concepts, task values, learning objectives, and achievement motives all have a significant impact on the students grades in a variety of academic subjects. Thus, the results deepen the understanding of the contribution of students' motivation to academic success.

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In the study of Johanson (2021), academic performance refers to the student's achievement in all academic subjects; it also involves the natural intellect, mental ability, and academic excellence of the learners. To assess the level of academic performance of the students, teachers review the students' classroom work performance, graduation rates, grade point average, and placement in class.

In addition, Tus's (2020) journal about students' academic performance embodies an essential component of the set of variables that determine a student's success. It also has a significant impact on education, especially by serving as a practical method to gauge students' learning progress.

Moreover, according to Mappadang et al. (2022), the academic interest of the students has a significant impact on the academic performance of the

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students. The higher the educational welfare of the students, the higher the quality of learning outcomes the students have.

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Synthesis

The current study examines the significance of inclusive education in promoting social inclusion and healthy personalities while acknowledging the risks of exclusion associated with it. Different writers provide insights on the topic, including the importance of creating a welcoming environment for all individuals, the struggles of implementing inclusive education, and the benefits of inclusive education for students with disabilities.

Kafia et al. emphasize the importance of inclusive education in promoting social inclusion, while Steigmann highlights the challenges in implementing it. Eke and Zahid et al. highlight the benefits of inclusive environments for students, that a positive environment improves the academic performances of the students. Dalgaard et al. highlight the need for educational theories explaining how inclusive education benefits special educational needs (SEN) students. Choi suggests a school-side application model for inclusive change, while Fitri recommends curriculum modification for SEN students. Hence, Szumski et al. pointed out that the inclusive classroom environment positively affects the academic achievement of students without SEN.

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Kart and Kart explain that inclusive education benefits students with disabilities in social and academic aspects but has different impacts on non-disabled students. Martynchuk emphasizes the need for a professional to balance educational attainment. Trujillo and Tanner suggest that inclusive education fosters campus belonging. Tainá et al. argue that inclusive education aims to examine a teacher's instructional strategies to meet student's individual needs. Mendoza and Heymann suggest that inclusive education training enhances teaching skills and insights.

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Moreover, Anabel's book states that implementing inclusive education in high schools can be challenging, but it is crucial. Bernardino et al. and Kursurkar et al. share the same thought that student motivation significantly impacts academic performance, encouraging hard work. Mehndroo and Vandana emphasize that motivation drives the needs, wants, and behaviors of the students, and academic interest significantly impacts students' academic performance.

Steinmayr et al. highlight that students' academic performance is influenced by factors like self-motivation, task values, learning objectives, and incentives, and enhancing self-motivation promotes deep learning and performance. Tus emphasizes academic achievement as a critical factor in success, while Johanson and Mappadang et al. suggest boosting self-motivation for deep learning and improved performance.

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UB emphasizes the significance of a learning environment that promotes inclusivity, ensuring equal opportunities for all students and fostering a sense of value and support. Opio et al. highlighted the significant impact of inclusive education on various learning environments, including self-efficacy and the impact of disability on students. Robb emphasizes the importance of a positive social environment in classrooms for healthy learning. Ackah-Jnr and Danso pointed out that a good physical environment, including ventilation, facility modifications, and inclusivity, is crucial for student accessibility. SE notes that diversity in the classroom fosters critical thinking and respect, making it a culturally responsive environment.

Kum, and Oclaret agreed that intrinsic motivation has a significant impact on the students learning and the student's academic performance. While Khaliq et.al. and Kum share the same thoughts that extrinsic motivation influences the student's drive to learn. Teraoka et al. and Capelle et al. note that effective learning and expectancy is an effective learning strategy to be used in teaching students, considering this factor can widely influence student motivation to learn. Golland, Li, and Singh agreed that inclusive education enhances student motivation and performance by promoting a sense of belongingness, particularly for those with disabilities, through positive peer relationships and effective teaching methods.

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Research Design

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In this study, the researchers employed a Quantitative-Correlational research design to investigate the link between inclusive education, students' motivation, and academic performance. This approach aids in determining the degree of association between the variables under investigation. Correlational research design is a type of non-experimental research methodology that examines the relationship between two or more variables. It is a practical approach for exploring the strength and direction of the relationship between variables and for generating hypotheses for further testing (Pallister, 2023).

Population and Sampling

The researchers used stratified random sampling, coming from the whole population of the Senior high school students of the Sto. Tomas Senior High School; the researchers randomly picked from the exact number of respondents needed for the study from the sample size given by the statistician.

Respondents of the Study

The study respondents were the selected senior high school students at Sto. Tomas enrolled in the school year 2023-2024. The researchers used stratified random sampling to select the respondents which were the selected Senior High School students of Sto. Tomas Senior High School. The researchers

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utilized the Taro Yamane formula to find the exact number of respondents from the population of senior high school students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School. Table A shows the whole population of Senior High school students from Grade 11 and Grade 12 and the sample size garnered using the Taro Yamane formula. Table A shows the respondents of the study.

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Table A
Respondents of the Study

Grade Level	Population	Sampling Size	Percentage	Respondents
Grade 11	705	155	50%	155
Grade 12	712	156	50%	156
Total	1417	311	100%	311

Research Instrument

The researchers used a self-made survey questionnaire to get the data needed for the study. The questionnaire determined the relationship between inclusive education, student motivation, and academic performance of the selected Senior High School students at the Sto. Tomas Senior High School.

The selected senior high school students answered the questionnaires by rating to what extent using a 4-point rating scale. The responses will be four (4) as "Strongly Agree," three (3) as "Agree," two (2) as "Disagree," and one (1) as

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"Strongly Disagree." The table below shows the Numerical value, Mean ranges, and Verbal interpretations.

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Numerical Value	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretations
4	4.00-3.25	Strongly Agree
3	3.24-2.50	Agree
2	2.49-1.75	Disagree
1	1.74-1.00	Strongly Disagree

Likert Four-Point Scale Range Interpretation (Alico & Guimba, 2015)

Validity and Reliability

The research instruments were established for the validity and reliability test. The first draft of the questionnaire was presented to the thesis adviser for suggestions, comments, and corrections. The panel's recommendation and modification were also considered for validating the questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by three validators: Teacher III from Tanauan City Integrated High School and two Teacher I from Tanauan City Integrated High School. The researchers asked permission from the principal to conduct the reliability test. To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the researchers conducted a Pre-Test and Post-Test on the thirty (30) randomly selected grade 11 and 12 senior high school students within the locale of Sto. Tomas Senior High

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School, since its demographic profile is similar to the target respondents of the present study. After getting the questionnaire, it was forwarded to the statistician to test its reliability. The reliability result was reliable based on Cronbach Alpha of internal consistency.

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Data Gathering Procedure

To determine the level of motivation of the students and the student's evaluation of inclusive education, the researchers utilized a self-made research questionnaire. Moreover, in collecting the data, the researcher wrote a letter to the division office of Sto. Tomas, followed by the principal of the school and advisers for permission to conduct a study. The data gathered is treated with the utmost confidentiality. In addition, the researchers conducted a pilot testing with thirty (30) respondents coming from the Senior High School students, to test the validity and reliability of the research instrument.

Ethical Consideration

A detailed briefing and essential details regarding the goal of the study were given to the respondents prior to its execution. The participants in the study voluntarily chose to participate through informed consent. Ensuring anonymity, confidentiality, and preventing potential harm requires that all material be handled

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with the highest confidentiality, with the research participants' names and identities kept private.

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Treatment of Quantitative Data

The gathered data underwent the statistical treatment outlined below in this study.

The researchers utilized the Taro Yamane formula to find the exact number of respondents from the population of senior high school students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School.

Yamane Formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Statement of Problem 1: The researchers used the percentage formula to identify the respondents' academic performance.

$$P=f/N \times 100\%$$

Where:

P is the percentage, f is the frequency, and N is the number of respondents.

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Statement of Problems 2 and 3: The researchers employed the weighted mean formula to gauge the student's motivation level and the students' evaluation of inclusive education.

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Formula:

$$\text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

N

Where;

x = level of preference

N = the no. of learners

$$\text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{fx_1 + fx_2 + \dots + fx_n}{f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_n}$$

Where;

X = level of preference

F = the frequency

Statement of Problems 4, 5, and 6: The researchers used the **Pearson R** correlational coefficient to measure the linear association between inclusive education and students' academic performance, between the students' motivation and students' academic performance, and between inclusive education and the

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student's motivation. It determined the significant relationship between the variables using this formula.

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Formula:

Where,

- r = Pearson Coefficient
- n = number of pairs of stock
- $\sum xy$ = sum of products of the paired stocks
- $\sum x$ = sum of the x scores
- $\sum y$ = sum of the y scores
- $\sum x^2$ = sum of the squared x scores
- $\sum y^2$ = sum of the squared y scores

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Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

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1. Learners' Proficiency Level

In terms of Learners' Proficiency Level, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the Proficiency level of the respondents

Learners Proficiency Level	Frequency	Percentage
79% and below	1	0.3
80-84%	30	9.7
85-89%	121	38.8
90% and above	159	51.1
Total	311	100

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents. The data shows that learners' proficiency level of 90% and above **159** responded with a percentage of **51.1%**. For **85-89%**, **121** respondents with a percentage of **38.8%**, **80-84%**, and **30** respondents with a percentage of **9.7%**. Lastly, in **79%** and below, one respondent with a percentage of **.3%**. All in all, **311** respondents answered the instruments. Thus, the result reveals that most of the respondents got a proficiency level of **90%** and above, and the researchers interpreted that most of the respondents were Proficient based on the DepEd Learner's Proficiency level.

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The result of this study can be related to the article of Kusurkar et al. (2013) that academic performance is positively impacted by motivation because it leads to a deeper study strategy and more significant study effort. Encouraging students' self-motivation is crucial to achieving a mindset of deep learning, great action, and, ultimately, good performance. According to Kusurkar et al., a student's motivation level plays a significant role in influencing the performance of the students, as evidenced by the high effort and effective study techniques.

In relation to the study's findings, the majority of the respondents falling within the 90% and above proficiency level indicates that majority of the respondents are performing at the highest level, which academic performance is positively impacted by motivation. This may suggest that the curriculum and instructional strategies are appropriately challenging and effective, and students are more likely to be engaged in learning. The learners become active participants in the learning process rather than passive recipients of information, which enhances the motivation and promotes a more profound understanding.

According to Steinmayr et al. (2019) started to determine the distinct ways in which various facets of students' motivation relate to variations in the academic performance. Research showed that, in addition to intelligence and past performance, students' ability self-concepts, task values, learning objectives, and achievement motives all have a significant impact on the grades in a variety of

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academic subjects. Thus, the results deepen the understanding of the contribution of students' motivation to academic success. This study supports the result of this study that the highest GWA of the selected Senior High School is 90% and above, suggesting that the school's ability to provide well-trained teachers who use effective instructional strategies and incorporate diverse learning modalities can enhance student engagement and understanding.

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2. Students' Evaluation of Inclusive Education

The following section presents the students' evaluation of inclusive education.

2.1. Learning Environment

In terms of the learning environment, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of inclusive education** of the respondents in terms of the learning environment. Table 2.1 shows the results of the conducted survey.

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Table 2.1
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive Education in
terms of Learning Environment

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. I constantly learn and grow freely with the support of my teachers	3.34	0.58	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers let us participate in every activity to have a deeper understanding of the topic.	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers value and appreciate my ideas in class.	3.33	0.63	Strongly Agree
4. My teacher uses a wide range of strategies in dealing the topics that apply to all kinds of learners.	3.43	0.65	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers treated us equally in the classroom.	3.27	0.81	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

Table 2.1 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of inclusive education in terms of the learning environment. The respondents Strongly Agree that *teacher uses a wide range of strategies in dealing the topics that apply to all kinds of learners*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.43** and standard deviation of **0.65**, and that *the teachers let the students participate in every activity to have a deeper understanding about the topic* with a mean of **3.35**, and standard deviation of **0.67**, also *student's constantly learn and grow freely with the support of the teachers* with the mean of **3.34**, and standard deviation of **0.58**.

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Moreover, the respondents also Agree that *teachers value and appreciate the students' ideas in class*, with a mean of **3.33** and a standard deviation of **0.63**; also, *the teachers treated everyone equally in the classroom*, with a mean of **3.27** and a standard deviation of **0.81**.

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Overall, based on the result of Table 2.1, it is seen that most of the respondents Strongly Agree that the teacher uses a wide range of strategies in teaching the subject, letting the students participate in every class activity to have a deeper understanding of the topic. The students are able to constantly learn and grow freely with the support of teachers. Additionally, a teacher who values and appreciates the ideas of the students and treating the learners equally in the classroom makes students much more interested in learning in the classroom. These indicators show that the respondents constantly learn in the classroom environment where teachers give equal opportunity for the students to participate in every activity.

Moreover, according to the article in UB (2024), said that the learning environment includes the intellectual, social, emotional, and physical environments, all of which will affect learning. Instructor-student interactions and the tone of the course may affect how students approach learning and work through difficulties. The demographics of students within the course and how peers interact also play a vital role in this environment. Furthermore, the study of

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Opio et al. (2023) mentioned that the inclusion of learners in secondary education has been fundamentally associated with the learning environment. However, little is known about the relationships between types of learning environments and inclusion when moderated by self-efficacy and mediated by disability status.

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Thus, the article of UB (2024) and the study of Opio et al. (2023) show that a learning environment that promotes teacher and student interaction and positive peer interaction affects students' learning. Moreover, the use of inclusive education is associated with the learning environment, which means that a classroom that promotes a sense of belonging and acceptance can influence the drive of the learners to study. Hence, these findings are consistent with the results of Table 2.1, which suggest that a learning environment that promotes teacher and student interaction and positive peer interaction can positively influence student learning.

2.2 Social environment

In terms of social environment, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of inclusive education** of the respondents in terms of social environment.

Table 2.2 shows the results of the conducted survey.

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Table 2.2
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive Education in
terms of Social Environment

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. My teachers encourage rapport with all kinds of learners.	3.14	0.67	Agree
2. My teachers assist me in improving my social abilities.	3.15	0.66	Agree
3. My teachers promote a sense of belonging among all students.	3.06	0.76	Agree
4. My teachers create positive interactions with everyone.	3.12	0.75	Agree
5. My teachers treated us equally in the classroom.	3.25	0.64	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.15	0.70	Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

Table 2.2 presents the indicators about the student's evaluation of inclusive education in terms of social environment; the respondents Agree that the *teachers treated everyone equally in the classroom*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.25** and standard deviation of **0.64** and that *the teachers assisted the students in improving social abilities* with a mean of **3.15**, and standard deviation of **0.66**, also that *the teachers encourage rapport to all kind of learners* with the mean of **3.14**, and standard deviation of **0.67**.

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Moreover, the respondents also Agree that *the teachers create a positive interaction with everyone*, with a mean of **3.12** and a standard deviation of **0.75**; also, *that the teachers promote a sense of belonging among all students*, with a mean of **3.06** and a standard deviation of **0.76**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 2.1, most of the respondents Agree that the teacher treated the student's equally, which are associated in improving the social abilities and encouraged rapport with all kinds of learners. Teachers do create a positive interaction with everyone and promote a sense of belonging among all students. Hence, a teacher who promotes a sense of belongingness to every student in the classroom encourages the learners to be more associated with socializing and interacting with classmates. These indicators show that the kind of social environment that a teacher creates inside the classroom can influence the child's social interest and can also affect the student's engagement in studying.

Furthermore, the finding is consistent with the related literature "Creating Low-Risk & Positive Social Environment for Diverse Students" by Robb, A. (2020); the article mentions that a low-risk environment has a deep connection to a positive social environment. A positive social environment promotes acceptance, kindness, forgiveness, and the opportunity to experience failure without consequences. This kind of environment helps the students to become

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acquainted with a healthy learning environment. It gives the learners the power to pursue education, build confidence and grow as a student.

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The study results from such to determine the impact of the social environment on the student along with the relationship of inclusive education; it has been determined that the quality of social skills between the student and teacher relationship influences student engagement in studying. Hence, these findings are consistent with the results of Table 2.2, which suggest that a positive social environment that the teacher has implemented in the classroom promotes a suitable environment for the students in learning.

2.3 Physical Environment

In terms of the physical environment, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of inclusive education** of the respondents in terms of physical environment.

Table 2.3 shows the results of the conducted survey.

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Table 2.3
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive Education in
terms of Physical Environment

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. The ventilation in the classroom gives a conducive environment that is suitable for learning.	3.31	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. The arrangement of the chairs in the classroom is suitable for all kinds of students.	3.33	0.62	Strongly Agree
3. The facilities in the school are accessible for all students, especially for students with physical disabilities	3.37	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. The lighting in the classroom is appropriate and comfortable for the students.	3.31	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. The physical layout of the school promotes equality for all learners.	3.25	0.72	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.31	0.65	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

Table 2.3 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of inclusive education in terms of the physical environment. The respondents Strongly Agree that *the facilities in the school are accessible for all students, especially for students with physical disabilities*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.37** and a standard deviation of **0.66**, and that *the arrangement of the chairs in the classroom is suitable for all kinds of student* with the mean **3.33**, and standard

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deviation of **0.62**, also *the ventilation in the classroom gives conducive environment that is suitable for learning* with the mean of **3.31**, and standard deviation of **0.63**.

Moreover, the respondents also Strongly Agree that *the lighting in the classroom is appropriate and comfortable for the student*, with a mean of **3.31** and standard deviation of **0.64**, and *the physical layout of the school promotes equality for all learners* with a mean **3.25**, and standard deviation of **0.72**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 2.3, most of the respondents Strongly Agree that a physical environment has an impact on the student's engagement in learning. Moreover, the facilities in school that are accessible for all students, especially for students with physical disabilities, the arrangement of the chairs in the classroom that are suitable for all kinds of students, the ventilation in the classroom that gives a conducive environment, the lighting in the classroom that is appropriate and comfortable for the students, and the physical layout of the school that promotes equality for all learners have a significant influence on the student's engagement in learning. These indicators show that the physical environment in the school, particularly in a classroom, has an impact on the students learning.

Moreover, the study by Ackah-Jnr and Danso (2018), entitled "Examining the physical environment of Ghanaian inclusive schools: how accessible,

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suitable and appropriate is such environment for inclusive schools?" mentioned that a poor-quality physical environment is less accessible for the students with special needs and less suitable for any physical activities. Therefore, improving the ventilation system, decorations, good architectural designs, modification of facilities, and physical landscape of schools is a must to promote accessibility for all kinds of students in the school.

Furthermore, Ackah-Jnr and Danso (2018) emphasized that a good quality physical environment in a school must be noticed to create an environment that will be suitable for learning. Hence, these findings are consistent with the results of Table 2.3, which suggest that a good quality physical environment is needed to achieve the student's engagement in learning.

2.4 Ethnic diversity

In terms of ethnic diversity, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of inclusive education** of the respondents in terms of ethnic diversity.

Table 2.4 shows the results of the conducted survey.

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Table 2.4
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive Education in
terms of Ethnic Diversity

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. My teachers value the diverse backgrounds of the students in class.	3.34	0.59	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers recognize the diversity of the student characteristics in a classroom.	3.35	0.68	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers give equal opportunity for the students to use their cultural knowledge in the classroom.	3.33	0.63	Strongly Agree
4. My teachers effectively promote a sense of belonging and acceptance regardless of my ethnic background.	3.43	0.66	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers reduce any discrimination among students.	3.27	0.81	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

Table 2.4 presents the indicators about the student's evaluation of inclusive education in terms of ethnic diversity; the respondents Strongly Agree that *the teachers effectively promote a sense of belonging and acceptance regardless of the ethnic background of every student*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.43**, and standard deviation of **0.66** and that *the teachers recognize the diversity of the*

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student characteristics in a classroom with mean **3.35**, and standard deviation of 0.68. Also, *the teachers value the diverse backgrounds of the students in class*, with a mean of 3.34 and a standard deviation of 0.59.

Moreover, the respondents also Strongly Agree that *the teachers give equal opportunity for the students to use the cultural knowledge in the classroom* with a mean of 3.33 and a standard deviation of 0.63, and *the teachers reduce any kinds of discrimination among students* with a mean 3.27, and standard deviation of 0.81.

Overall, based on the result in Table 2.4, it is seen that most of the respondents Strongly Agree that a teacher who effectively promotes a sense of belonging and acceptance, regardless of the background of the students, values and recognizes the different characteristics of every learner, give equal opportunity for everyone and most of all reduces any discrimination in the classroom has an influence in the student's engagement in the studying. These indicators show that the diversity of learners and a teacher's role in promoting a sense of belongingness and acceptance for every learner inside the classroom has an impact on the students' learning.

Moreover, the article of SE (2019), entitled "The Benefits of Inclusion and Diversity in the Classroom", mentioned that diversity in the classroom

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encourages students to value and appreciate the different perspectives of every student, fostering critical thinking and understanding. It also promotes creativity, decision-making, and problem-solving. Teachers should create a culturally responsive learning environment, fostering respect and understanding among students about the differences among the students. This approach promotes creativity and problem-solving and encourages critical thinking. Overall, diversity in the classroom fosters a more inclusive and respectful learning environment.

Overall, the article of SE (2019) is consistent with the findings of Table 2.4, which presents the impacts of ethnic diversity on the students in inclusive education, as the role of the teacher in a diverse classroom in creating an environment that fosters an understanding environment that respects the differences of the students, that can help the students to grow as a learner and given equal opportunity.

3. Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education

The following section presents the **Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education**.

3.1 Intrinsic Motivation

In terms of intrinsic motivation, the indicators were explored. The table

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below indicates the **Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education** of the respondents in terms of intrinsic motivation.

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Table 3.1 shows the results of the conducted survey,

Table 3.1
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
in terms of Intrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. Completing my activities and assignments beforehand helps me feel more in control of my academic workload.	3.33	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. I love doing schoolwork because it gives me a sense of fulfillment.	3.09	0.78	Agree
3. My enjoyment in doing my task motivates me to keep doing my academic responsibility.	3.30	0.67	Strongly Agree
4. The opportunities for creativity and self-expression that are enhance in the classroom give me motivation to learn.	3.38	0.62	Strongly Agree
5. A supportive and encouraging learning environment enhances my innate motivation.	3.42	0.63	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.31	0.67	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

Table 3.1, presents the indicators about the students' motivation in terms of intrinsic motivation. The respondents Strongly Agree that *a supportive and*

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encouraging learning environment enhances the innate motivation of the students, which obtained the highest mean of **3.42** and standard deviation of **0.63**, and that *the opportunities for creativity and self-expression that are enhanced in the classroom gives motivation to learn* with a mean of **3.38**, and standard deviation of **0.62**, also *that completing the activities and assignments beforehand helps the students feel more in control of the academic workload* with the mean of **3.33**, and standard deviation of **0.63**.

Moreover, the respondents also Strongly Agree that *the enjoyment in doing tasks motivates the students to keep doing the academic responsibilities*, with a mean of **3.30** and a standard deviation of **0.67**. Also, *the learners love doing schoolwork because it gives a sense of fulfillment*, with a mean of **3.09** and a standard deviation of **0.78**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 3.1, it is seen that most of the respondents Strongly Agree that a supportive and encouraging learning environment, an opportunity for creativity and self-expression, completing activities and assignments beforehand, enjoyment in doing the tasks, and a sense of fulfillment in doing school works, enhances the motivation of the students. The indicators indicate that intrinsic motivation significantly enhances students' motivation to engage in academic activities.

This finding is consistent with the related literature "The Effects of Intrinsic

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and Extrinsic Motivation on Student Learning Effectiveness (Case Study: International Students of Estonian Entrepreneurship University of Applied Sciences)" by Kum, B.A. (2022). The study found that motivation has a big influence on human behavior, that motivation is a course of action or inspiration used by a person to meet the desired outcome. Hence, intrinsic motivation has a positive impact on the student's learning effectiveness. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation significantly impacts students' motivation and performance, as it fosters passion and drive for learning.

In addition, according to Oclaret, V. (2021), in "Impact of Academic Intrinsic Motivation Facets on Student's Academic Performance," the study found that intrinsic motivation has a positive impact on academic performance. Students are found to perform well academically and are very interested in learning. Furthermore, Kum (2022) and Oclaret (2021) agree that intrinsic motivation has a significant impact on the student's learning and the student's academic performance. Hence, these findings are consistent with the results of Table 3.1, which suggest that intrinsic motivation greatly influences the student's drive to learn and doing the academic responsibilities

3.2 Extrinsic Motivation

In terms of extrinsic motivation, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education** of

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the respondents in terms of extrinsic motivation.

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Table 3.2 shows the results of the conducted survey,

Table 3.2
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
in terms of Extrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. The presence of tangible rewards, like certificates or prizes, boosts my drive to accomplish academic objectives.	3.32	0.78	Strongly Agree
2. Receiving high grades is a primary motivator for me to study and complete assignments.	3.41	0.72	Strongly Agree
3. The school's rewards system motivates me equally, regardless of my background.	3.27	0.70	Strongly Agree
4. The fear of negative consequences, such as failing grades or disappointing others, motivated me to work harder.	3.24	0.75	Agree
5. The presence of competitive environments significantly influences my motivation to succeed.	3.25	0.76	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.30	0.74	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

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Table 3.2 presents the indicators of the student's motivation in terms of extrinsic motivation. The respondents Strongly Agree that *receiving high grades is a primary motivator for the learners to study and complete assignments*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.41** and standard deviation of **0.72** and that *the presence of tangible rewards, like certificates or prizes, boosts the students drive to accomplish academic objectives* with the mean of **3.32**, and standard deviation of **0.78**, also that *the school's rewards system motivates the learners equally, regardless of the different background* with the mean of **3.27**, and standard deviation of **0.70**.

Moreover, the respondents also Strongly Agree that *the presence of competitive environments significantly influence the student's motivation to succeed*, with a mean of **3.25** and standard deviation of **0.76**, also that *the fear of negative consequences, such as failing grades or disappointing others, motivated the students to work harder* with the mean of **3.24**, and standard deviation of **0.75**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 3.2, it is seen that most of the respondents Strongly Agree that receiving high grades, completing the assignments, and the presence of tangible rewards, the school's reward system, a competitive environment, and the negative consequences like failing grades, gives motivation in learning. These indicators show that extrinsic motivation influences the student's motivation in learning. This finding is consistent with the

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related literature, "Extrinsic Motivation and Student's Academic Achievement: A Correlational Study" by Khaliq et al. (2023). The study found that the motivating factors persistently influence human behavior; it accurately shows the factors that encourage a person. Moreover, extrinsic motivation has a positive impact on the student's academic success; the presence of attaining rewards such as high grades and praise from peers extrinsically motivated the learners. Furthermore, the study by Kum (2022), "The Effects of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation on Student Learning Effectiveness (Case Study: International Students of Estonian Entrepreneurship University of Applied Sciences)", found that the factors that push a person to achieve the desired course of action is the motivation. Hence, extrinsic motivation has a favorable impact on student learning effectiveness and so as in academic performance.

Thus, Khaliq et al. (2023) and Kum (2022) agreed that extrinsic motivation influences the student's drive to learn. Extrinsic motivation has a positive impact on the student's academic success and academic performance. Hence, these findings are consistent with the results of Table 3.2, which suggest that extrinsic motivation has a significant impact on the student's academic success and academic performance; in the presence of receiving rewards in return for doing the academic task, the learners are extrinsically motivated.

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3.3 Affective Motivational Aspects

In terms of affective, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education** of the respondents in terms of affective.

Table 3.3 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 3.3
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
in terms of Affective Motivational Aspects

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. I feel sense of belonging within my academic community.	3.28	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. I am motivated to exert the necessary effort to achieve academic success.	3.35	0.65	Strongly Agree
3. I have been driven to do better in my academic performance because my teacher supports me consistently.	3.23	0.69	Agree
4. My teacher recognizes my emotional being.	3.14	0.75	Agree
5. Engaging in collaborative learning enhances my sense of purpose.	3.19	0.68	Agree
Overall Mean	3.24	0.68	Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

Table 3.3 presents the indicators of the student's motivation in inclusive education in terms of affective. The majority of the respondents Agree that *students are motivated to exert the necessary effort to achieve academic*

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success, which obtained the highest mean of **3.35** and standard deviation of **0.65**, and that *the students feel a sense of belonging within the academic community* with a mean of **3.28**. The standard deviation of **0.63**, also the respondents Agree that *learners are driven to do better in the academic performance because the teacher supports everyone in the class consistently*, with a mean of **3.23** and a standard deviation of **0.69**.

Moreover, the respondents also Agree that also that *engaging in collaborative learning enhances the learner's sense of purpose*, with a mean of **3.19** and a standard deviation of **0.68**; also, *the teacher recognizes the emotional being of every student*, with a mean of **3.14** and a standard deviation of **0.75**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 3.3, it is seen that most of the respondents Agree that the students possess certain affective that are important for feeling a sense of belongingness within the academic community, which is motivated to exert the necessary effort to achieve academic success, driving the learners to do better in academic performance, when a teacher recognizes the emotional being of the students, and engaging in collaborative learning. These indicators show that a classroom environment that fosters the affective and emotional being of the learners affects the engagement in learning.

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According to Teraoka et al. (2020), "Affective Learning in Physical Education: A Systematic Review," said that affective outcomes have four themes: motivation, self-concept, emotional response, and resilience, which affect the student's engagement in learning. Moreover, effective teaching strategies that include offering students a choice, promoting explicit criticism, placing a strong emphasis on growth, and posing reasonable questions give the students engagement and motivation to study. Affective learning widely influences this factor. Hence, to create an effective teaching strategy, it should acknowledge the factors that affect effective learning as this still influences the student's motivation to learn.

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Overall, Teraoka et al. (2020) supports the result of the study presented in Table 3.3, which suggests that effective motivation is one of the factors that drive learners. If the teacher uses effective learning in teaching, it could motivate the students to be more associated with learning.

3.4 Expectancy Theory of Motivation

In terms of expectancy, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education** of the respondents in terms of expectancy.

Table 3.4 shows the results of the conducted survey,

Table 3.4
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
in terms of Expectancy Theory of Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. I have high expectations when I know I do my best in a given task.	3.49	1.87	Strongly Agree
2. My efforts will always result in success in the classroom.	3.19	0.73	Agree
3. My actions will always lead to positive academic outcomes.	3.23	0.71	Agree
4. Doing my academic responsibilities will benefit me in the future.	3.55	0.61	Strongly Agree
5. I will always expect myself to perform well in class.	3.26	0.79	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35	0.94	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation
4.00-3.25- Strongly Agree, 3.24-2.50- Agree, 2.49-1.75- Disagree, 1.74-1.00- Strongly Disagree

Table 3.4 presents the indicators of the level of student motivation in inclusive education in terms of expectancy. The respondents Strongly Agree that *doing the academic responsibilities will benefit students in the future*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.55** and standard deviation of **0.61**, and that *students have high expectations when the best is given for the task* with the mean of **3.49**, and standard deviation of **1.87** also that *learners always expect their selves to perform well in class* with the mean of **3.26**, and standard deviation of **0.79**.

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Moreover, the respondents also Agree that the *students' actions will always lead to positive academic outcomes*, with a mean of **3.23** and a standard deviation of **0.72**; also, *the learner's efforts will always result success in the classroom*, with a mean of **3.19** and a standard deviation of **0.73**.

Overall, based on the result of Table 3.4, it is seen that most of the respondents Strongly Agree that doing academic tasks will benefit individuals, having high expectations when giving the best efforts, expecting a good performance, and believing that actions will lead to a positive outcome and efforts will lead to success. These indicators shows that the students' expectation of themselves when giving a good performance has an impact on the students' performances in school. Moreover, in the study of Capelle et al. (2023), "Trajectories in quantity and quality of motivation and study activities among university students as exams approach," said that the expectation and task value beliefs give a complete framework for characterizing a person's overall motivation to pursue an activity, like a study task, and subsequently fuel study behavior.

Overall, Capelle et al. (2023) supports the result of the study presented in Table 3.4, which suggests that expectancy contributes to the learning and academic tasks of the students. The expectancy plays a massive role in the student's drive to learn. It gives motivation to the learners to expect more about

themselves especially when the learner performs well in class. Expectancy affects the behavior of the students to want more in academic achievement. This motivation can help the students to be much engage in learning.

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4. Significant relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance.

The researchers determined the significant relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance in the selected Senior High School. The significant relationship was determined using the **Pearson r Coefficient**.

Table 4.

Significant Relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance

Table 4: *Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis*

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision (H₀)	Interpretation
Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance	0.135	0.018	Reject H ₀	Significant (Very Weak Positive Correlation)

p<0.05=Significant, p>0.05=Not Significant

Table 4 presents the relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance. In terms of Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance, with an R-value of 0.135 or P-value of 0.018,

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thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there was a significant relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance, though it is a very weak positive correlation. A very weak positive correlation are observed in inclusive education and students' academic performance, it is because the inclusive education can create a huge impacts to every learner that can influence the students engagement in learning at school, on the other hand, inclusive education can be not effective to some learners that the idea of socializing and interacting in daily basis is not one of the students hobby or wants, this can be a reason why a very weak correlation is observed in the data, other than that, the inclusive education still has a significant impact on students' academic performance.

Using the Pearson R correlation, the researchers came up with the result that can be seen in Table 4. The table shows that the relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance has a significant relationship.

The study "Academic Achievement of the Students without Special Educational Needs in Inclusive Classrooms: A Meta-analysis" by Szumski, G. et al. (2017) supports the significant relationship found between inclusive education and students' academic performance. This study shows that the inclusive classroom environment positively affects the academic

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achievement of students without special educational needs (SEN). The study also emphasizes that inclusive education is associated with the academic achievement of the students.

Furthermore, according to the article by Choi (2021), in urban elementary and elementary/middle schools, it has been demonstrated that the school-wide applications model (SAM) has the potential to be a successful model for inclusive school-wide change that will increase equity-based inclusive education practices and improve student achievement for all kids. Since inclusive education serves students with a variety of learning requirements and cultural backgrounds in addition to those with impairments, schools must comprehend how inclusive education enhances the institution.

Additionally, the study and article mentioned above highlight the role of inclusive settings in students' academic achievement. Moreover, the application of inclusive education practices in the school institution can improve the students' achievement. Since inclusive education serves a variety of learners, school institutions can comprehend the effects of inclusive education on the learners as this positively influences the academic performance of the students.

In summary, both the study and article emphasize the role of Inclusive Education in enhancing Students' Academic Performance, which is consistent with the findings of the study on the significant relationship between Inclusive

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Education and Students' Academic Performance.

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5. Significant relationship between the Students' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance.

The researchers determined the significant relationship between the Students' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance of the Learners. The significant relationship was determined using **Pearson's r Coefficient**.

Table 5.
Significant Relationship between Students' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance

Table 5: *Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis*

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision (H₀)	Interpretation
Students' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance	0.159	0.005	Reject H ₀	Significant (<i>Very Weak Positive Correlation</i>)

p<0.05=Significant, p>0.05=Not Significant

Table 5, presents the relationship between the Student's Motivation and the Students' Academic Performance. In terms of the Student's Motivation and the Students' Academic Performance, the R-Value of **0.159** or P-Value of **0.005**, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there was a significant relationship between the Student's Motivation and the Students' Academic

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Performance. Additionally, a very weak positive correlation is observed between students' motivation and students' academic performance, it is because all students have different types of motivation in life, just like the different characteristics of every student, a learner have different kind of motivation that can be used motivate a person to be more engage in learning new things at school.

Using the Pearson R correlation, the researchers came up with the result that can be seen in Table 5. The table shows that the relationship between students' Motivation and the Students' Academic Performance, has a significant relationship.

The study by Steinmayr et al. (2019) started to determine the distinct ways in which various facets of students' motivation relate to variations in the academic performance. Research showed that, in addition to intelligence and past performance, students' ability self-concepts, task values, learning objectives, and achievement motives have a significant impact on the grades of the learners in a variety of academic subjects. Thus, the results deepen the understanding of the contribution of students' motivation to academic success.

Moreover, according to Mappadang et al. (2022), the academic interest of the students has a significant impact on the academic performance of the students. The higher the educational welfare of the students, the higher the quality

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of learning outcomes the students have.

The various factors mentioned in the two studies, such as ability self-concepts, task values, learning objectives, and incentives, all contribute to shaping students' attitudes and behaviors towards learning. For instance, a student who have a strong belief in the abilities and value in doing the tasks assigned are likely to perform better academically. Hence, the factors that have been mentioned also influence students' motivation. Moreover, understanding these different aspects of motivation can help educators tailor interventions and strategies to support students in achieving the academic goals. Additionally, it highlights the importance of fostering a positive learning environment that promotes intrinsic motivation and a growth mindset.

In summary, both studies emphasize the importance of Student Motivation to enhance Students' Academic Performance, which is consistent with the findings of the study on the significant relationship between Students' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance.

6. Significant relationship between Inclusive Education and the Student's Motivation.

The researchers determined the significant relationship between the Inclusive Education and Student Motivation of the Learners. The significant relationship was determined using **Pearson's r Coefficient**.

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Table 6.
Significant Relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation

Table 6: *Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis*

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation	0.675	<0.01	Reject H ₀	Significant (Strong Positive Correlation)

p<0.05=Significant, p>0.05=Not Significant

Table 6 presents the relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation. In terms of inclusive Education and Students' Motivation with the RR-Value of **.675** or P-Value of **.001**, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there was a significant relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation. A strong positive correlation is observed in the findings it is because an inclusive environment that a teacher create in the classroom can create a huge impact in motivating the students to be more engage in learning.

Using the Pearson R correlation, the researchers came up with the result that can be seen in Table 6. The table shows that the relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation has a significant relationship. The researchers also concluded that in terms of Inclusive Education it can enhance the students' Motivation, so that it has a significant relationship.

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The study "Inclusive Classrooms and How They Impact Academic Motivation and Engagement Among Students with Learning Disabilities by Golland (2019) found that when inclusive education is used in teaching or co-taught, it could affect the academic motivation of the students and engagement in learning. Moreover, co-taught classrooms that are inclusive have a positive impact on academic motivation and engagement among students with disabilities.

The study by Li and Singh (2022), entitled "Inclusive Learning Environment Can Improve Student Learning and Motivation Beliefs," said that students' perception of the inclusiveness of the learning environment significantly impacts the motivational beliefs and performance in the course. Perceived recognition and sense of belonging are critical factors in predicting overall physics identity and self-efficacy, respectively. While peer interaction has a more minor direct effect, it still plays a crucial role in shaping students' sense of belonging and recognition. Instructors should focus on strategies to enhance students' interactions with peers to improve outcomes.

The correlation between peer interaction, sense of belonging, and perceived recognition indicates that these factors are interconnected and influence each other within the learning environment. The model incorporating all three inclusiveness of learning environment constructs is the most effective in explaining the variance in outcome constructs compared to other models. This

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comprehensive model is deemed the most productive for understanding student performance and motivation in the course.

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Hence, the study by Golland (2019), Li and Singh (2022) agreed that inclusive education positively influences student's motivation and performance. Hence, inclusive education promotes a sense of belongingness for every learner, especially for those who have a disability. The use of inclusive education in teaching and a positive peer relationship positively influences the student's motivation.

In summary, both studies emphasize the role of Inclusive Education in the classroom and its influence on the Student's Motivation which is consistent with the findings of the study on the significant relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation.

7. What action plan can be proposed to promote inclusive education and enhance students' motivation and academic performance?

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Action Plan: Enhancing Inclusive Education and Student's Motivation

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Key areas	Goals/Objectives	Activities/strategies	Personnel Involved	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicators
Inclusive Education	To improve the academic performance of the students by enhancing the classroom management that supports students' learning.	Hold a training session for all students' that covers various study skills, including effective note-taking, exam preparation and time management. Teach students some practical strategies like focused study sessions, mind mapping for organizing information, and active recall to reinforce learning.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students • Teachers • Parents • School Administrator 	Year-round 2023-2024	Teachers Supervision in training Writing materials	85% will increase the students' academic performance.
	To foster the sense of belongingness and acceptance in the classroom to maintain the student's engagement in learning.	Parents involvement in the process of promoting inclusivity in the classroom, focusing on abilities not in disabilities of every student's, engaging equality for all learners.		Parents support and cooperation	85% Parents' cooperation and support to the diverse learners in the classroom and promoting equal opportunity for all the students to excel academically.	
	To support the inclusive education and students' academic success.	Offer training for oral communication and public speaking for every student to further develop their skills and confidence. Providing equal opportunity for all the students to excel in their different intelligences.		Teachers Supervision in training	90% increase in developing students' confidence to speak in public and explore their different talents in any field.	
	To use inclusive education in teaching the students.	Workshop for the teachers in using inclusive education to increase the student's engagement in learning.		Teachers' cooperation in the activity.	90% of the teachers uses inclusive education in teaching their lesson.	

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Key areas	Goals/ Objectives	Activities/ Strategies	Personnel Involved	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicators
Student's Motivation	To improve the student's motivation in learning process and their academic performance.	Peer tutoring program, which aims to pair a motivated students that excel academically with peers who may needs additional support and motivation, this will be helpful in engaging collaborative learning, motivating each other and learning from each other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students • Teachers • Parents • School Administrator 	Every end of the quarter – 1 Year	Teachers Supervision in the program	80% of students continued to pursue their academic goals with the help of their peers that influence them to be motivated in learning.
	To foster the student's engagement in learning that will be helpful in improving their academic performance	Providing a tangible reward such as certificates, praises and some recognition to celebrate the learner's achievement in academics.		Certificates of Recognition	80% increase rate in motivating the students in learning.	
	To contribute to the learner's personal growth and drive in learning.	Offer an activity that aims to show the learners hidden talents and interest in any field.		Facilities Sports, Art Materials Music Instruments Writing Materials	Year-round 2023-2024	90% Increase students' engagement in school.
	To incorporate the use of motivation in the teacher's lesson plan and in school and classroom activities	Workshop for the teachers that explains the role of motivation in capturing the student's engagement and interest in learning.		Teachers' participation the activity	Before the First month of School Year start.	Almost 90% of the teachers includes motivation before they start their classes.

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Conclusions

Based on the findings, there is a significant relationship between inclusive education and students' academic performance, students' motivation and students' academic performance, and inclusive education and students' motivation, thus, the hypothesis is accepted. The majority of the learners who participated in the study demonstrated proficiency in the subject assessed, indicating the students' evaluation of inclusive education and the level of student motivation. Further research could delve into the significant relationships between inclusive education and students' academic performance, students' motivation and students' academic performance, and inclusive education and students' motivation.

The study revealed a notable significant relationship between inclusive education and students' academic performance. Inclusive education can influence the learners' academic performance, suggesting that an environment that promotes a sense of belongingness, acceptance, and equal opportunity for all the students in the classroom can significantly influence the students' academic performance. Moreover, inclusive education has been divided into four factors: the learning environment, social environment, physical environment, and ethnic diversity; these factors have a favorable impact on improving the student's academic performance. Hence, a weak positive correlation has been determined

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between inclusive education and students' academic performance, though it is still significant.

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Significantly, the study found that there is a significant correlation between students' motivation and students' academic performance, though it is fragile. This indicates that student's motivation has a substantial impact on improving the academic performance of the students. Other factors that contribute to the level of motivation of the learners are intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, affective, and expectancy. This factor plays a significant role in determining the academic achievement of the respondents.

Conversely, a significant relationship with a strong positive correlation was also observed between inclusive education and students' motivation. This highlights the positive impact of inclusive education on students' motivation. Thus, an environment in the classroom that promotes a positive interaction with the diverse group of learners that values and appreciates the differences of every individual can significantly improve the student's motivation in learning.

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the proficiency level of the learners, the evaluation of inclusive education, the student's level of motivation, and the significant relationships between these three factors. The findings suggest that while an inclusive education setting is perfectly implemented and maintained in every classroom, it can enhance the student's drive to learn as this helps the

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learners in increasing motivation, as this also plays a role in student's academic performance, these factors are crucial in promoting a healthy environment in the classrooms and improved the learning practices of the students. Further research is warranted to explore additional factors and refine the educational approach to optimize learning outcomes.

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Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations can be made to facilitate the effective implementation of Inclusive Education affecting Students' Motivation and Academic Performance. Schools play a pivotal role in creating environments where all students feel valued, supported, and empowered to learn and thrive. Offer ongoing professional development opportunities for educators to enhance the knowledge and skills in inclusive education. Training sessions can cover topics such as cultural competency, differentiated instruction, behavior management, and working with students with special needs, fostering a positive and supportive school culture where diversity is celebrated, and all students feel safe, respected, and valued. This involves promoting inclusive language and behaviors, addressing bullying and discrimination, and providing resources for social-emotional learning and mental health support; school leaders should model inclusive behaviors and values, demonstrating a commitment to diversity, equity, and inclusion in all aspects of

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school operations and decision-making.

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Teachers should assess the individual strengths, weaknesses, learning styles, and preferences of each student. This could involve pre-assessments, observations, discussions with students, and input from parents or previous teachers; teachers can adapt the teaching methods, materials, and assessments to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities. For example, providing visual aids, hands-on activities, or auditory resources can cater to different learning preferences, and establishing a positive and inclusive classroom culture where diversity is celebrated, and respect is valued is essential for motivating students.

Students should demonstrate respect and acceptance towards peers, regardless of differences in abilities, backgrounds, or identities. The students can actively challenge stereotypes, biases, and discriminatory behaviors, fostering a culture of inclusivity and belonging. Students can educate peers and teachers about the importance of inclusivity and diversity.

Parents play a crucial role in supporting and promoting inclusive education; parents can collaborate with teachers and school administrators to ensure that the child's individual needs and strengths are recognized and addressed. By sharing information about the child's learning style, preferences, and any

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challenges that may face, parents can work together with educators to develop appropriate support strategies and accommodations.

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Future researchers exploring the intersection of inclusive education and student motivation have a pivotal role in advancing educational practices and policies. By conducting empirical studies, it can deepen our understanding of the complex dynamics at play and contribute valuable insights to the field. These researchers will need to be well-versed in educational psychology, special education, and research methodologies to design rigorous studies and interpret findings accurately. Moreover, it should possess strong interpersonal skills to collaborate with diverse stakeholders, including students, teachers, parents, and policymakers.

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APPENDICES

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Appendix A: Letter of Validation

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 24, 2024

CHRISTIAN D. TEJERESAS, LPT
Master Teacher I
Tanauan City Integrated High School

Sir:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled **"Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School"**

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the Self-Made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very Truly Yours,
JAKE R. ROMAN
V. Monares
LENARD VIEN E. MONARES
Merry Ann D. Bernardo
MERRY ANN D. BERNARDO
Robel T. Cornejo
ROBEL T. CORNEJO
Sheri Ann M. Lazaro
SHERI ANN M. LAZARO
Researchers

Noted:
MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:
Christian D. Tejeresas
CHRISTIAN D. TEJERESAS, LPT
Master Teacher I

Brgy. Trapiche 1, Tanauan City, Batangas | Tel. No. (043) 702 - 6979; (043) 702-4160; (043) 722-3366; (043) 786-2113
E-mail: tanauancitycollege@gmail.com | URL: <https://www.facebook.com/tanauancitycollegeofficial>

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Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : CHRISTIAN D. TERERESAS
 Highest Educational Qualification : MAEd GC
 Position Held : MT
 Field of Specialization : Psychology
 Signature : _____

Directions:

A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.

B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

4	-	very valid	2	-	less valid
3	-	moderately valid	1	-	need for revalidation

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	4
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II. Level of Students Motivation

A. Intrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	4
	II.A.2	1	2	3	4
	II.A.3	1	2	3	4
	II.A.4	1	2	3	4
	II.A.5	1	2	3	4

B. Extrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	4
	II.B.2	1	2	3	4

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	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
C. Affective					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
D. Expectancy					
Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	4
	II.D.2	1	2	3	4
	II.D.3	1	2	3	4
	II.D.4	1	2	3	4
	II.D.5	1	2	3	4
III. Students evaluation of Inclusive Education					
A. Learning Environment					
Value Item	III.A.1	1	2	3	4
	III.A.2	1	2	3	4
	III.A.3	1	2	3	4
	III.A.4	1	2	3	4
	III.A.5	1	2	3	4
B. Social Environment					
Value Item	III.B.1	1	2	3	4
	III.B.2	1	2	3	4
	III.B.3	1	2	3	4
	III.B.4	1	2	3	4
	III.B.5	1	2	3	4
C. Physical Environment					

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Value item

III.C.1	1	2	3	4
III.C.2	1	2	3	4
III.C.3	1	2	3	4
III.C.4	1	2	3	4
III.C.5	1	2	3	4

D. Ethnic Diversity

Value item

III.D.1	1	2	3	4
III.D.2	1	2	3	4
III.D.3	1	2	3	4
III.D.4	1	2	3	4
III.D.5	1	2	3	4

Remarks/Recommendation

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

Approved to be used as presented

Approved to be used with revisions as indicated

Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

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3. Inclusive education promotes a sense of belonging among all students.				
4. My teachers promote a positive environment and create positive interactions with everyone.				
5. All the teachers and students show respect to all kinds of learners. <i>each other.</i>				
Physical Environment - <i>part of learning environment</i>				
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of physical environment are:.....	4	3	2	1
1. In an inclusive education setting, the classroom gives a pleasant environment that is suitable for learning. <i>window ventilation.</i>				
2. The position of the chairs in the classroom is suitable for all kinds of students.				
3. The facilities in school are accessible for all students, especially for the students with physical disabilities.				
4. The physical structure of the classroom is suitable and comfortable for the students. <i>lighting.</i>				
5. The physical structure of the school promotes equality for all learner.				
Ethnic Diversity				
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of ethnic diversity are:.....	4	3	2	1
1. My teachers value and acknowledge the different life experiences of the students in class.				
2. My teachers recognize the diversity of the student characteristics in a classroom. <i>backgrounds</i> that has been influenced by gender, cultural heritage, socio-economic background, ability/disability, and personality. .				
3. My teachers give equal opportunity for the students to use their cultural knowledge in the classroom.				
4. My teachers are unbiased in treating the students even if we have different religious beliefs. <i>balanced</i>				
5. My teachers express the importance of recognizing ethnic diversity in teaching in the classroom. <i>with the questions why focus all on the teachers?</i>				

II. Students' Motivation

Intrinsic				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1
1. Completing my activities and assignments beforehand helps me feel more in control of my academic workload.				
2. I am often intrinsically motivated to do my schoolwork because I find it fulfilling. <i>naturally</i>				
3. My enjoyment in doing my task motivates me to keep doing my academic responsibility.				
4. The opportunities for creativity and self-expression that are enhanced in the classroom give me the motivation to learn.				
5. A supportive and encouraging learning environment enhances my intrinsic motivation. <i>innate</i>				
Extrinsic				

over an over-coming of physical & social calls

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I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1
1. The availability of tangible rewards, such as certificates or prizes, positively impacts my motivation to achieve academic goals.				
2. Receiving high grades is a primary motivator for me to study and complete assignments.				
3. The school's rewards system motivates all the students equally, regardless of their backgrounds.				
4. The fear of negative consequences, such as failing grades or disappointing others, motivated me to work harder.				
5. The presence of competitive environments and opportunities to compare my performance with others increases my motivation to succeed.				
Affective - <i>emotion</i>				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1
1. I feel a sense of belonging within my academic community, which enhances my motivation. <i>inspired</i>				
2. I am motivated to put in the effort required to succeed academically. <i>inspired</i>				
3. I am motivated to improve my academic performance because my teacher supports me consistently. <i>have drive</i>				
4. My teacher recognizes my emotional being. Thus, it gives me the motivation to do my activities.				
5. Interacting with peers and engaging in collaborative learning enhances my motivation. <i>sense of purpose</i>				
Expectancy				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1
1. I have big expectations when I know I will do my best in an activity. <i>a given task.</i>				
2. Receiving the expected outcome of my test and other activities motivates me to study even more in the future.				
3. My actions will always lead to good academic outcomes.				
4. Doing my academic responsibilities will benefit me in the future.				
5. I always expect myself to perform well in class.				

by Vroom.

- effort
- performance
- outcome.

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Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : CHRISTIAN D. TEJENECS
Highest Educational Qualification : MAED GC
Position Held : MASTER TEACHER I
Field of Specialization : PSYCHOLOGY
Signature : [Signature] 1/26/24

Directions:

A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.

B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

- | | | | | | |
|---|---|------------------|---|---|-----------------------|
| 4 | - | very valid | 2 | - | less valid |
| 3 | - | moderately valid | 1 | - | need for revalidation |

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
------------	-------	---	---	---	----------

II. Students evaluation of Inclusive Education

A. Learning Environment

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.2	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.3	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.4	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.A.5	1	2	3	<u>4</u>

B. Social Environment

Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	<u>4</u>
	II.B.2	1	2	3	<u>4</u>

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	II.B.3	1	2	3	1
	II.B.4	1	2	3	3
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
C. Physical Environment					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
D. Ethnic Diversity					
Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	4
	II.D.2	1	2	3	4
	II.D.3	1	2	3	4
	II.D.4	1	2	3	4
	II.D.5	1	2	3	4
III. Level of Students Motivation					
A. Intrinsic Motivation					
Value Item	III.A.1	1	2	3	4
	III.A.2	1	2	3	4
	III.A.3	1	2	3	4
	III.A.4	1	2	3	4
	III.A.5	1	2	3	4
B. Extrinsic Motivation					
Value Item	III.B.1	1	2	3	4
	III.B.2	1	2	3	4
	III.B.3	1	2	3	4
	III.B.4	1	2	3	4
	III.B.5	1	2	3	4

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C. Affective Motivation

Value item

III.C.1	1	2	3	4
III.C.2	1	2	3	4
III.C.3	1	2	3	4
III.C.4	1	2	3	4
III.C.5	1	2	3	4

D. Expentancy Motivation

Value item

III.D.1	1	2	3	4
III.D.2	1	2	3	4
III.D.3	1	2	3	4
III.D.4	1	2	3	4
III.D.5	1	2	3	4

Remarks/Recommendation

Overall Rating

Please check (√) appropriate rating.

- Approved to be used as presented
- Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
- Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

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REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 24, 2024

MARIEL ANGELOU U. OLAN, LPT, MEM, MAED
Master Teacher I
Tanauan City Integrated High School

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "**Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School**"

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the Self-Made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,
JAKE R. ROMAN

LENARD VIEN E. MONARES

MERRY ANN D. BERNARDO

RODEL T. CORNEJO

SHERI ANN M. LAZARO
Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

MARIEL ANGELOU U. OLAN, LPT, MEM, MAED
Master Teacher I

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

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TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

School of Education

Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students

Dear Respondents,

We are the students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School AY 2023-2024".

Be assured that the information you provide will be used for this study alone and will be treated with confidentiality. With your cooperation, we are grateful. Thank you, and God bless you.

The Researchers

See comments on the back

PART I. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Name: _____

Age: _____

Grade Level: _____

1. What is your General Weighted Average in First (1st) semestral grading? _____

PART II. STUDENTS' EVALUATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION STATEMENTS

Directions: The following are set of indicators that will describe the evaluation of the respondents in inclusive education and examine the students' motivation. Using the 4 - point scale shown below, indicate the degree of your agreement and disagreement; in the following statement indicators of the variables described below. All responses that will be gathered by this research shall be treated with confidentiality.

please put a check mark on the column that corresponds to your answer

4 - Strongly Agree 3 - Agree 2 - Disagree 1 - Strongly Disagree

I. Inclusive Education

A. Learning Environment

My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of learning environment... <i>ok</i>	4	3	2	1
1. I constantly learn and grow freely with the support of my teachers. ✓				
2. My teachers let all the students participate in all activity where we can understand the topic deeply. <i>allow every student to take part in any activity</i>				
3. I can express my ideas in the class without feeling any discrimination. ✓				
4. My teacher uses different teaching strategies in teaching the topics that apply to all kinds of learners. <i>wide range of teaching strategies creating</i>				

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5. We are all treated the same in the classroom. <i>My teachers treated as equality in the classroom.</i>					
Social Environment					
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of social environment...	4	3	2	1	
1. It encourages friendship to all kind of learners. /					
2. It helps me develop my social skills. /					
3. It promotes a sense of belonging among all students. /					
4. My teachers create positive interactions with everyone. /					
5. All teachers and students show respect to each other. /					
Physical Environment					
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of physical environment...	4	3	2	1	
1. The ventilation in the classroom gives pleasant ^{conductive} environment that is suitable for learning.					
2. The position ^{arrangement} of the chairs in the classroom is suitable for all kinds of students.					
3. The facilities in school are accessible for all students, especially for the students with physical disabilities.					
4. The lighting in the classroom is appropriate and comfortable for the students. /					
5. The physical structure ^{layout} of the school promotes equality for all learner.					
Ethnic Diversity					
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of ethnic diversity...	4	3	2	1	
1. My teachers value the different ^{diverse} backgrounds of the students in class. /					
2. My teachers recognize the diversity of the student characteristics in a classroom. /					
3. My teachers give equal opportunity for the students to use their cultural knowledge in the classroom.					
4. It ^{my teachers} effectively promotes a sense of belonging and acceptance regardless of my ethnic background. /					
5. It ^{my teachers} reduces any kind of discrimination among students. /					
PART III.					
II. Students' Motivation					
Intrinsic					
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1	
1. Completing my activities and assignments beforehand helps me feel more in control of my academic workload. /					
2. I am naturally motivated to do my schoolwork because I find it fulfilling. /					
3. My enjoyment in doing my task motivates me to keep doing my academic responsibility. /					
4. The opportunities for creativity and self-expression that are enhanced in the classroom give me the motivation to learn. /					
5. A supportive and encouraging learning environment enhances my innate motivation. /					
Extrinsic					
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1	

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1. The availability of tangible rewards, such as certificates or prizes, positively impacts my motivation to achieve academic goals. ✓				
2. Receiving high grades is a primary motivator for me to study and complete assignments. ✓				
3. The school's rewards system motivates all the students equally, regardless of their backgrounds. ✓				
4. The fear of negative consequences, such as failing grades or disappointing others, motivated me to work harder. ✓				
5. The presence of competitive environments increases my motivation to succeed.				
Affective				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1
1. I feel a sense of belonging within my academic community. ✓				
2. I am inspired to put in the effort required to succeed academically. ✓ <i>I am motivated to exert the necessary effort to achieve academic success.</i>				
3. I have driven to ^{do better in} improve my academic performance because my teacher supports me consistently.				
4. My teacher recognizes my emotional being. ✓				
5. Engaging in collaborative learning enhances my sense of purpose. ✓				
Expectancy				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1
1. I have ^{high} big expectations when I know I do my best in a given task. ✓				
2. Receiving the ^{positive results} expected outcome of my activities motivates me to study even more in the future. ✓				
3. My actions will always lead to good academic outcomes. ✓				
4. Doing my academic responsibilities will benefit me in the future. ✓				
5. I always expect myself to perform well in class. ✓				

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Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : MARIEL ANGELOU UMIRIG-DLAN
 Highest Educational Qualification : DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE & LITERATURE
 Position Held : MASTER TEACHER I / GUEST LECTURER
 Field of Specialization : ENGLISH LANGUAGE & LITERATURE; EDUC. MANAGEMENT
 Signature :

Directions:

- A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.
 B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

4	-	very valid	2	-	less valid
3	-	moderately valid	1	-	need for revalidation

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	(4)
------------	-------	---	---	---	-----

II. Students evaluation of Inclusive Education

A. Learning Environment

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.2	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.3	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.4	1	2	3	(3)
	II.A.5	1	2	3	(4)

B. Social Environment

Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.2	1	2	3	(4)

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	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
C. Physical Environment					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
D. Ethnic Diversity					
Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	4
	II.D.2	1	2	3	4
	II.D.3	1	2	3	4
	II.D.4	1	2	3	4
	II.D.5	1	2	3	4
III. Level of Students Motivation					
A. Intrinsic Motivation					
Value Item	III.A.1	1	2	3	4
	III.A.2	1	2	3	4
	III.A.3	1	2	3	4
	III.A.4	1	2	3	4
	III.A.5	1	2	3	4
B. Extrinsic Motivation					
Value Item	III.B.1	1	2	3	4
	III.B.2	1	2	3	4
	III.B.3	1	2	3	4
	III.B.4	1	2	3	4
	III.B.5	1	2	3	4

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C. Affective Motivation

Value item	1	2	3	
III.C.1				4
III.C.2				4
III.C.3				4
III.C.4				4
III.C.5				4

D. Expentancy Motivation

Value item	1	2	3	
III.D.1				4
III.D.2				4
III.D.3				4
III.D.4				4
III.D.5				4

Remarks/Recommendation

- kindly adhere on all the revisions / suggestions indicated in the paper. !!

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

Approved to be used as presented

Approved to be used with revisions as indicated

Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

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REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 24, 2024

VENICE S. PAGASPAS, LPT, MAED
Teacher III
Tanauan City Integrated High School

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled **"Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School"**

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the Self-Made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,
JAKE R. ROMAN

LENARD VIEN E. MONARES

MERRY ANN D. BERNARDO

ROBERT T. CORNEJO

SHERI ANN M. LAZARO
Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

Aut
VENICE S. PAGASPAS, LPT, MAED
Teacher III

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Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : Verice S. Pagaspas
 Highest Educational Qualification : PhDE - English (GAR)
 Position Held : Teacher III
 Field of Specialization : English
 Signature : [Signature]

Directions:

- A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.
- B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

- | | |
|----------------------|---------------------------|
| 4 - very valid | 2 - less valid |
| 3 - moderately valid | 1 - need for revalidation |

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	4
------------	-------	---	---	---	---

II. Level of Students Motivation

A. Intrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	④
	II.A.2	1	2	③	4
	II.A.3	1	2	3	④
	II.A.4	1	2	3	④
	II.A.5	1	2	3	④
	II.A.6	1	2	3	4
	II.A.7.	1	2	3	4

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B. Extrinsic Motivation

Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	4
	II.B.2	1	2	3	4
	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
	II.B.6	1	2	3	4
	II.B.7.	1	2	3	4

C. Affective

Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
	II.C.6	1	2	3	4
	II.C.7	1	2	3	4

D. Expectancy

Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	4
	II.D.2	1	2	3	4
	II.D.3	1	2	3	4
	II.D.4	1	2	3	4
	II.D.5	1	2	3	4
	II.D.6	1	2	3	4
	II.D.7.	1	2	3	4

III. Students evaluation of Inclusive Education

A. Learning Environment

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Value Item	1	2	3	4
III.A.1	1	2	3	4
III.A.2	1	2	3	4
III.A.3	1	2	3	4
III.A.4	1	2	3	4
III.A.5	1	2	3	4
III.A.6	1	2	3	4
III.A.7.	1	2	3	4
B. Social Environment				
Value Item	1	2	3	4
III.B.1	1	2	3	4
III.B.2	1	2	3	4
III.B.3	1	2	3	4
III.B.4	1	2	3	4
III.B.5	1	2	3	4
III.B.6	1	2	3	4
III.B.7.	1	2	3	4
C. Physical Environment				
Value item	1	2	3	4
III.C.1	1	2	3	4
III.C.2	1	2	3	4
III.C.3	1	2	3	4
III.C.4	1	2	3	4
III.C.5	1	2	3	4
III.C.6	1	2	3	4
III.C.7.	1	2	3	4

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D. Ethnic Diversity

Value item

III.D.1	1	2	3	④
III.D.2	1	2	3	④
III.D.3	1	2	③	4
III.D.4	1	2	3	④
III.D.5	1	2	3	④
III.D.6	1	2	3	4
III.D.7.	1	2	3	4

Remarks/Recommendation

- Be mindful of the basic grammar errors
- Be mindful of PARALLELISM
- change some of the formats as indicated in the corrected questionnaires
- Put translation (Filipino)

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

- Approved to be used as presented
- Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
- Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

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Title

Directions: The following are set of indicators that will describe the evaluation of the respondents in **inclusive education** and examine the **students' motivation**. Using the 4 – point scale shown below, indicate the degree of your agreement and disagreement in the following statement indicators of the variables described below. All responses that will be gathered by this research shall be treated ^{as} confidentially.

4 – Strongly Agree 3 – Agree 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree

3- Inclusive Education

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION <i>Learning Env</i>				
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of learning environment are.....	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1. In an inclusive education setting, I constantly learn and grow freely with the support of my teacher(s).				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2. My teacher(s) let all the students participate in every activity where we can understand the topic deeply.				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3. I can express my ideas in the class without feeling any discrimination.				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4. My teacher uses different teaching strategies in teaching her topics that apply to all kinds of learners.				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5. We are all treated the same in the classroom.				

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION <i>Social Env</i>				
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of social environment are.....	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1. The inclusive education setting encourages friendship between students with different disabilities.				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2. My teacher(s) promote(s) a positive environment and create(s) positive interactions with everyone.				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3. The inclusive education setting helps me develop my social skills.				

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4. The teacher(s) and students show respect to all kinds of learners.				
5. Inclusive education promotes a sense of belonging among all students.				

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION — Physical	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of physical environment are.....				
1. In an inclusive education setting, the instructor gives attention to providing enough desks in the classroom to make all the students feel comfortable.				
2. The layout of our classroom is suitable for the way of learning.				
3. The lighting in the classroom is appropriate during lectures.				
4. The classroom is large enough to accommodate all the students.				
5. The chairs in the classroom are suitable for all types of students.				

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION — Ethnic	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of ethnic diversity are.....				
1. My teacher(s) value and acknowledge the different life experiences of the students in class.				
2. My teacher(s) recognize the diversity of the student characteristics in a classroom that has been influenced by gender, cultural heritage, socio-economic background, ability/disability, and personality.				
3. My teacher(s) give(s) equal opportunity for the students to use				

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their cultural knowledge in the classroom.				
4. My teachers are unbiased in treating the students even if we have different religious beliefs.				
5. My teacher(s) express the importance of recognizing ethnic diversity in teaching in the classroom.				

II - Students' Motivation

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION - Intrinsic				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1. Completing my activities and assignments beforehand helps me feel more in control of my academic workload.				
2. I am often intrinsically motivated to do my schoolwork because I find it fulfilling.				
3. My enjoyment in doing my task motivates me to keep doing my academic responsibility.				
4. The opportunities for creativity and self-expression that are enhanced in the classroom give me the motivation to learn.				
5. A supportive and encouraging learning environment enhances my intrinsic motivation.				

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION - Extrinsic				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1. The availability of tangible rewards, such as certificates or prizes, positively impacts my motivation to achieve academic goals.				

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2. Receiving high grades is a primary motivator for me to study and complete assignments.				
3. The school's rewards system motivates all the students equally, regardless of their backgrounds.				
4. The fear of negative consequences, such as failing grades or disappointing others, motivated me to work harder.				
5. The presence of competitive environments and opportunities to compare my performance with others increases my motivation to succeed.				

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION - Affective				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1. I feel a sense of belonging within my academic community, which enhances my motivation.				
2. I am motivated to put in the effort required to succeed academically.				
3. I am motivated to improve my academic performance because my teacher supports me consistently.				
4. My teacher recognizes my emotional being. Thus, it gives me the motivation to do my activities.				
5. Interacting with peers and engaging in collaborative learning enhances my motivation.				

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION - Expectancy				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	Strongly Agree (4)	Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1. I have big expectations when I know I will do my best in an activity.				

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2. Receiving the expected outcome of my test and other activities motivates me to study even more in the future.				
3. My actions will always lead to good academic outcomes.				
4. Doing my academic responsibilities will benefit me in the future.				
5. I always expect myself to perform well in class.				

Source: _____

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Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : VENICE S. PAGASPAS
Highest Educational Qualification : PHD E - English (CAR)
Position Held : Teacher III
Field of Specialization : English
Signature :

Directions:

A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.

B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

4	-	very valid	2	-	less valid
3	-	moderately valid	1	-	need for revalidation

I. Level of Academic Performance

A. General Weighted Average

Value item	I.A.1	1	2	3	④
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II. Students evaluation of Inclusive Education

A. Learning Environment

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	④
	II.A.2	1	2	3	④
	II.A.3	1	2	3	④
	II.A.4	1	2	3	④
	II.A.5	1	2	3	④

B. Social Environment

Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	④
	II.B.2	1	2	3	④

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	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
C. Physical Environment					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
D. Ethnic Diversity					
Value Item	II.D.1	1	2	3	4
	II.D.2	1	2	3	4
	II.D.3	1	2	3	4
	II.D.4	1	2	3	4
	II.D.5	1	2	3	4
III. Level of Students Motivation					
A. Intrinsic Motivation					
Value Item	III.A.1	1	2	3	4
	III.A.2	1	2	3	4
	III.A.3	1	2	3	4
	III.A.4	1	2	3	4
	III.A.5	1	2	3	4
B. Extrinsic Motivation					
Value Item	III.B.1	1	2	3	4
	III.B.2	1	2	3	4
	III.B.3	1	2	3	4
	III.B.4	1	2	3	4
	III.B.5	1	2	3	4

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C. Affective Motivation

Value item

III.C.1	1	2	3	(4)
III.C.2	1	2	3	(4)
III.C.3	1	2	3	(4)
III.C.4	1	2	3	(4)
III.C.5	1	2	3	(4)

D. Expentancy Motivation

Value item

III.D.1	1	2	3	(4)
III.D.2	1	2	3	(4)
III.D.3	1	2	3	(4)
III.D.4	1	2	3	(4)
III.D.5	1	2	3	(4)

Remarks/Recommendation

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

- Approved to be used as presented
- Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
- Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

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Appendix B: Research Instrument

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Dear Respondents,

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "Inclusive Education Students Motivation and Academic Performance".

Be assured that the information you provide will be used for this study alone and will be treated confidentially. With your cooperation, we are grateful. Thank you, and May God bless you.

The Researchers

I. Directions: Put a check (✓) on the space provided that corresponds to your General Weighted Average (GWA) during the 1st Quarter S.Y. 2023-2024.

____(5) 90 and above ____ (1) 74 and below
____(4) 85 – 89
____(3) 80 – 84
____(2) 75 – 79

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Directions: The following statements describe the evaluation of the respondents in **inclusive education** and examine the **students' motivation**. Please put a check mark on the column that corresponds to your answer. Using the 4 – point scale shown below, indicate the degree of your agreement and disagreement:

4 – Strongly Agree 3 – Agree 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree

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A. Learning Environment				
My evaluation in inclusive education in terms of learning environment...	4	3	2	1
1. I constantly learn and grow freely with the support of my teachers.				
2. My teachers let us participate in every activity to have a deeper understanding about the topic.				
3. My teachers value and appreciate my ideas in class.				
4. My teacher uses wide range of strategies in dealing the topics that apply to all kinds of learners.				
5. My teachers treated us equally in the classroom.				

B. Social Environment				
	4	3	2	1
1. My teachers encourage rapport to all kind of learners.				
2. My teachers assist me in improving my social abilities.				
3. My teachers promote a sense of belonging among all students.				
4. My teachers create positive interactions with everyone.				
5. All teachers and students show respect to each other.				

A. Physical Environment				
	4	3	2	1
1. The ventilation in the classroom gives conducive environment that is suitable for learning.				
2. The arrangement of the chairs in the classroom is suitable for all kinds of students.				
3. The facilities in school are accessible for all students, especially for the students with physical disabilities.				
4. The lighting in the classroom is appropriate and comfortable for the students.				
5. The physical lay-out of the school promotes equality for all learner.				

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B. Ethnic Diversity				
	4	3	2	1
1. My teachers value the diverse backgrounds of the students in class.				
2. My teachers recognize the diversity of the student characteristics in a classroom.				
3. My teachers give equal opportunity for the students to use their cultural knowledge in the classroom.				
4. My teachers effectively promote a sense of belonging and acceptance regardless of my ethnic background.				
5. My teachers reduce any kind of discrimination among students.				

STUDENTS' MOTIVATION

A. Intrinsic				
I am feeling motivated in inclusive education setting because...	4	3	2	1
1. Completing my activities and assignments beforehand helps me feel more in control of my academic workload.				
2. I love doing school work because it gives me a sense of fulfillment.				
3. My enjoyment in doing my task motivates me to keep doing my academic responsibility.				
4. The opportunities for creativity and self-expression that are enhanced in the classroom give me the motivation to learn.				
5. A supportive and encouraging learning environment enhances my innate motivation.				

B. Extrinsic				
	4	3	2	1
1. The presence of tangible rewards, like certificates or prizes, boosts my drive to accomplish academic objectives.				
2. Receiving high grades is a primary motivator for me to study and complete assignments.				
3. The school's rewards system motivates me equally, regardless of my background.				
4. The fear of negative consequences, such as failing grades or disappointing others, motivated me to work harder.				
5. The presence of competitive environments significantly influences my motivation to succeed.				

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B. Affective				
	4	3	2	1
1. I feel a sense of belonging within my academic community.				
2. I am motivated to exert the necessary effort to achieve academic success.				
3. I have driven to do better in my academic performance because my teacher supports me consistently.				
4. My teacher recognizes my emotional being.				
5. Engaging in collaborative learning enhances my sense of purpose.				

Expectancy				
	4	3	2	1
1. I have high expectations when I know I do my best in a given task.				
2. My efforts will always result in success in the classroom.				
3. My actions will always lead to positive academic outcomes.				
4. Doing my academic responsibilities will benefit me in the future.				
5. I always expect myself to perform well in class.				

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Appendix C: Result of Pearson's R

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VALIDITY TEST

RESEARCH TITLE:	INCLUSIVE EDUCATION, STUDENTS' MOTIVATION AND TITLE: ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE SELECTED SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS
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To test the validity of the questionnaire, the statistician utilized Pearson's r Correlation. According to Ahrens et al. (2020), to assess construct validity, Pearson's correlation can be employed. Pearson's correlation is commonly used to verify the intensity of the existing linear association between variables, and it measures the linear association between quantitative variables. The table below shows the critical values for Pearson's r .

This table will be use as reference to interpret the significance of each variables/indicator to come up with an interpretation.

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Table for Critical values of Pearson's *r*

<i>For a two-tailed test</i>				
df:	0.1	0.05	0.02	0.01
1	.988	.997	.9995	.9999
2	.9	.95	.98	.99
3	.805	.878	.934	.959
4	.729	.811	.882	.917
5	.669	.754	.833	.874
6	.622	.707	.789	.834
7	.582	.666	.75	.798
8	.549	.632	.716	.765
9	.521	.602	.685	.735
10	.497	.576	.658	.708
11	.476	.553	.634	.684
12	.458	.532	.612	.661
13	.441	.514	.592	.641
14	.426	.497	.574	.623
15	.412	.482	.558	.606
16	.4	.468	.542	.59
17	.389	.456	.528	.575
18	.378	.444	.516	.561
19	.369	.433	.503	.549
20	.36	.423	.492	.537
21	.352	.413	.482	.526
22	.344	.404	.472	.515
23	.337	.396	.462	.505
24	.33	.388	.453	.496
25	.323	.381	.445	.487
26	.317	.374	.437	.479
27	.311	.367	.43	.471
28	.306	.361	.423	.463
29	.301	.355	.416	.456
30	.296	.349	.409	.449

Using this table as reference, calculating the degrees of freedom where $30 - N = 28$, we compare the computed *p* value to the critical values in the Pearson's *r* table. To interpret the test as valid, $p > df$, where the *df* is 28, with a 95% confidence (0.05).

The following are the results of the validity test using Pearson's *r* Coefficient to test the construct validity of each indicator in the research question.

For the second test, the statistician utilized the Pearson's *r* Coefficient to test the convergent and discriminant validity of the indicators.

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PRETEST: INCLUSIVE EDUCATION QUESTIONNAIRE

	ENP1	ENP2	ENP3	ENP4	ENP5	ENP1	ENP2	ENP3	ENP4	ENP5	ENP1	ENP2	ENP3	ENP4	ENP5	EDP1	EDP2	EDP3	EDP4	EDP5
ENP1 Pearson Correlation	1	.757 ^{**}	.247	.365 [*]	.524 ^{**}	.408 [*]	-.189	.004	.318	.359	.185	.151	.119	.166	.351	.408 [*]	.558 ^{**}	.309	.309	.053
ENP1 Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.188	.047	.003	.025	.317	.658	.087	.051	.327	.426	.531	.380	.058	.025	.001	.097	.097	.703
ENP1 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP2 Pearson Correlation	.757 ^{**}	1	.198	.099	.469 ^{**}	.323	.024	.258	.086	.423 [*]	.283	.150	.310	.345	.515 ^{**}	.480 ^{**}	.480 ^{**}	.213	.213	-.163
ENP2 Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.295	.604	.009	.081	.901	.169	.651	.020	.130	.430	.096	.062	.004	.007	.007	.258	.258	.388
ENP2 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP3 Pearson Correlation	.247	.198	1	.117	.410 [*]	.590 ^{**}	.287	.273	.215	.302	.056	-.067	.043	-.093	.192	.219	.219	.295	.295	.129
ENP3 Sig. (2-tailed)	.188	.295		.538	.024	.001	.124	.144	.253	.105	.769	.725	.823	.624	.310	.246	.246	.113	.113	.496
ENP3 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP4 Pearson Correlation	.365 [*]	.099	.117	1	.286	.408 [*]	.155	.205	.595 ^{**}	.492 [*]	-.107	-.132	-.064	-.009	.088	.257	.257	.154	.309	.315
ENP4 Sig. (2-tailed)	.047	.604	.538		.126	.025	.414	.278	.001	.006	.573	.487	.737	.963	.645	.171	.171	.416	.097	.090
ENP4 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP5 Pearson Correlation	.524 ^{**}	.469 ^{**}	.410 [*]	.286	1	.634 ^{**}	.284	.686 ^{**}	.456 [*]	.758 ^{**}	.015	-.085	.165	.144	.460 [*]	.408 [*]	.408 [*]	.463 ^{**}	.463 ^{**}	.315
ENP5 Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.009	.024	.126		.000	.129	.000	.011	.000	.939	.656	.385	.446	.011	.025	.025	.010	.010	.090
ENP5 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP1 Pearson Correlation	.408 [*]	.323	.590 ^{**}	.408 [*]	.634 ^{**}	1	.234	.568 ^{**}	.355	.628 ^{**}	-.009	-.024	.032	-.075	.306	.282	.426 [*]	.196	.489 ^{**}	.200
ENP1 Sig. (2-tailed)	.025	.081	.001	.025	.000		.212	.001	.054	.000	.961	.900	.867	.694	.101	.131	.019	.300	.006	.290
ENP1 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP2 Pearson Correlation	-.189	.024	.287	.155	.284	.234	1	.448	.135	.351	-.032	-.157	.122	.066	.127	.071	.071	.111	.111	.020
ENP2 Sig. (2-tailed)	.317	.901	.124	.414	.129	.212		.013	.477	.057	.868	.409	.520	.727	.505	.710	.710	.558	.558	.881
ENP2 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP3 Pearson Correlation	.084	.258	.273	.205	.686 ^{**}	.568 ^{**}	.448	1	.388 [*]	.703 ^{**}	.229	.052	.303	.338	.443 [*]	.225	.339	.273	.507 ^{**}	.350
ENP3 Sig. (2-tailed)	.658	.169	.144	.278	.000	.001	.013		.034	.000	.223	.783	.104	.067	.014	.232	.067	.145	.004	.052
ENP3 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP4 Pearson Correlation	.318	.086	.215	.595 ^{**}	.456 [*]	.355	.135	.388 [*]	1	.313	.076	.049	.104	.145	.229	.355	.355	.403 [*]	.538 ^{**}	.732 ^{**}
ENP4 Sig. (2-tailed)	.087	.651	.253	.001	.011	.054	.477	.034		.092	.688	.796	.586	.445	.223	.054	.054	.027	.002	.000
ENP4 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP5 Pearson Correlation	.359	.423 [*]	.302	.492 ^{**}	.758 ^{**}	.628 ^{**}	.351	.703 ^{**}	.313	1	.090	-.021	.181	.374 [*]	.490 ^{**}	.502 ^{**}	.375 [*]	.302	.431 [*]	.176
ENP5 Sig. (2-tailed)	.051	.020	.105	.006	.000	.000	.057	.000	.092		.637	.912	.337	.042	.006	.005	.041	.105	.017	.352
ENP5 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP1 Pearson Correlation	.185	.283	.056	-.107	.015	.009	-.032	.229	.076	.090	1	.683 ^{**}	.612 ^{**}	.737 ^{**}	.592 ^{**}	.287	.473 ^{**}	.000	.190	.097
ENP1 Sig. (2-tailed)	.327	.130	.769	.573	.939	.961	.868	.223	.688	.637		.000	.000	.000	.001	.124	.008	1.000	.316	.611
ENP1 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP2 Pearson Correlation	.151	.150	-.067	-.132	-.085	-.024	-.157	.052	.049	-.021	.683 ^{**}	1	.431 [*]	.666 ^{**}	.330	.245	.514 ^{**}	.153	.336	.218
ENP2 Sig. (2-tailed)	.426	.430	.725	.187	.656	.900	.409	.783	.796	.912	.000		.017	.000	.075	.192	.004	.420	.070	.246
ENP2 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP3 Pearson Correlation	.119	.310	.043	-.064	.165	.032	.122	.303	.104	.181	.612 ^{**}	.431 [*]	1	.550 ^{**}	.589 ^{**}	.119	.206	.148	.296	-.045
ENP3 Sig. (2-tailed)	.531	.096	.823	.737	.385	.867	.520	.104	.586	.337	.000	.017		.002	.001	.531	.275	.434	.112	.812
ENP3 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP4 Pearson Correlation	.166	.345	-.093	-.009	.144	-.075	.066	.338	.145	.374 [*]	.737 ^{**}	.666 ^{**}	.550 ^{**}	1	.677 ^{**}	.508 ^{**}	.425 [*]	.170	.255	.159
ENP4 Sig. (2-tailed)	.380	.062	.624	.963	.446	.694	.727	.067	.445	.042	.000	.000	.002		.000	.004	.019	.368	.173	.400
ENP4 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP5 Pearson Correlation	.351	.515 ^{**}	.192	.088	.460 [*]	.306	.127	.443 [*]	.229	.490 ^{**}	.592 ^{**}	.330	.589 ^{**}	.677 ^{**}	1	.639 ^{**}	.472 ^{**}	.114	.284	.145
ENP5 Sig. (2-tailed)	.058	.004	.310	.645	.011	.101	.505	.014	.223	.006	.001	.075	.001	.000		.000	.008	.550	.128	.444
ENP5 N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
ENP1 Pearson	.408 [*]	.480 ^{**}	.219	.257	.408 [*]	.282	.071	.225	.355	.502 ^{**}	.287	.245	.119	.588 ^{**}	.639 ^{**}	1	.713 ^{**}	.636 ^{**}	.342	.325

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LEN4	Pearson Correlation	.106	.154	.248	.091	.288	.476	.524	.257	.143	.282	.184	.263	.308	.098	.541	.482
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.578	.416	.186	.631	.128	.008	.003	.171	.450	.161	.331	.160	.097	.608	.002	.010
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
LEN5	Pearson Correlation	.181	.116	.514	-.061	.317	.282	.286	.408	.469	.282	.118	.099	.308	.000	.101	.644
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.338	.543	.004	.749	.088	.131	.126	.025	.009	.161	.534	.604	.097	1.000	.594	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SENP1	Pearson Correlation	.139	.196	.476	.074	.201	.424	.408	.282	.400	.259	.075	.480	.312	.217	.172	.627
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.465	.300	.008	.697	.288	.019	.025	.131	.028	.167	.694	.007	.094	.250	.365	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SENP2	Pearson Correlation	.071	.279	.124	.224	.258	-.052	-.017	.071	.138	.274	.171	.024	-.005	-.035	.098	.271
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.710	.136	.515	.234	.173	.785	.928	.710	.473	.143	.367	.901	.978	.853	.607	.147
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SENP3	Pearson Correlation	.111	.390	.469	.138	.160	.171	.325	.454	.418	.206	.159	.133	.026	.025	.034	.663
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.561	.033	.009	.473	.398	.368	.080	.012	.022	.274	.400	.484	.892	.897	.858	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SENP4	Pearson Correlation	.082	.405	.422	.080	.485	.607	.595	.487	.465	.483	.180	.373	.269	.255	.354	.700
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.629	.027	.020	.678	.010	.000	.001	.006	.010	.007	.398	.043	.151	.174	.055	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
SENP5	Pearson Correlation	-.004	.172	.419	-.105	.177	.189	.359	.502	.244	.106	-.044	.147	.029	.027	.038	.581
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.982	.362	.021	.581	.350	.318	.051	.005	.194	.577	.817	.438	.880	.886	.843	.001
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
PENP1	Pearson Correlation	.195	.190	.094	.231	.145	.061	.185	.009	.104	.038	.016	-.121	-.153	-.180	-.332	.394
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.303	.316	.620	.219	.445	.748	.327	.961	.585	.851	.933	.523	.419	.342	.073	.031
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
PENP2	Pearson Correlation	.066	.061	-.150	.129	-.103	-.114	-.038	-.114	-.010	-.092	-.250	-.046	-.273	-.077	-.188	.229
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.730	.748	.430	.498	.587	.549	.843	.550	.957	.627	.183	.811	.144	.685	.321	.224
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
PENP3	Pearson Correlation	.206	.208	.302	.328	.165	-.215	.119	.206	-.043	.123	.030	-.070	-.048	-.084	.026	.403
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.275	.271	.105	.079	.385	.255	.531	.275	.823	.516	.874	.715	.801	.622	.892	.027
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
PENP4	Pearson Correlation	-.075	.085	.020	.039	-.007	-.006	.079	.258	.165	-.048	-.130	-.109	.381	-.054	-.299	.372
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.694	.655	.918	.837	.971	.974	.679	.168	.383	.800	.492	.567	.038	.778	.109	.043
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
PENP5	Pearson Correlation	.139	-.057	.283	.150	.274	.143	.175	.389	.455	.295	-.073	.061	.027	.072	-.050	.597
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.464	.766	.130	.430	.143	.452	.354	.034	.011	.113	.703	.751	.887	.706	.794	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
EDP1	Pearson Correlation	-.005	.049	.026	.074	.319	.319	.257	.426	.400	.397	-.050	.323	.033	.402	.043	.589
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.980	.797	.891	.697	.086	.086	.171	.019	.028	.030	.793	.081	.864	.028	.822	.001
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
EDP2	Pearson Correlation	.282	.196	.026	.171	.319	.319	.408	.139	.400	.259	.075	.323	.172	.217	.043	.704
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.131	.300	.891	.367	.086	.086	.025	.465	.028	.167	.694	.081	.363	.250	.822	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
EDP3	Pearson Correlation	.049	.250	-.153	.033	.362	.394	.154	.342	.337	.331	.128	.213	.238	.443	.088	.506
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.797	.183	.419	.863	.049	.031	.416	.064	.068	.074	.501	.258	.206	.014	.645	.004
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30

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EDP4	Pearson Correlation	.049	.400*	.191	.033	.362	.287	.463	.489	.464	.331	.128	.373	.381	.443	.219	.734*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.797	.029	.311	.863	.049	.124	.010	.006	.010	.074	.501	.042	.038	.014	.244	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
EDP5	Pearson Correlation	-.050	.255	.274	-.067	.349	.403	.315	.200	.409*	.410*	-.196	.109	.219	.162	.112	.495*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.793	.173	.143	.724	.059	.027	.090	.290	.025	.024	.300	.567	.246	.384	.556	.005
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
IMOP1	Pearson Correlation	.106	.463*	-.106	.396*	.286	.144	.206	.406*	.143	.262	.315	.263	.455*	.293	.135	.334*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.578	.010	.576	.030	.126	.448	.274	.025	.450	.161	.090	.160	.012	.116	.476	.071
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
IMOP2	Pearson Correlation	.249	.560*	.419*	.238	-.031	.003	.359	-.004	-.084	.350	.286	.423*	.152	.027	.378*	.295*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.185	.001	.021	.210	.870	.987	.051	.982	.660	.058	.125	.020	.423	.886	.039	.114
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
IMOP3	Pearson Correlation	.375*	.560*	.221	.065	.177	.281	.625*	.249	.135	.106	.176	.285	.152	.027	.151	.620*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.041	.001	.240	.732	.350	.132	.000	.185	.478	.577	.352	.127	.423	.886	.425	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
IMOP4	Pearson Correlation	.033	.523*	.368*	.060	.241	.385*	.455*	.731*	.526*	.530*	.097	.385	.321	.511*	.083	.894*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.864	.003	.045	.755	.199	.035	.012	.000	.003	.003	.609	.035	.083	.004	.661	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
IMOP5	Pearson Correlation	.429*	.351	.369*	.029	.529*	.535*	.812*	.429*	.518*	.414*	.224	.608*	.459*	.222	.423*	.661*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.018	.057	.045	.880	.003	.002	.000	.018	.003	.023	.234	.000	.011	.239	.020	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	.353	.556*	.429*	.335	.550*	.489*	.670*	.557*	.533*	.571*	.328	.508*	.409*	.337	.295	.1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.055	.001	.018	.070	.002	.006	.000	.001	.002	.001	.076	.004	.025	.069	.113	
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

RELIABILITY TEST

RESEARCH TITLE:

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION, STUDENTS' MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE SELECTED SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the statistician tested the INTERNAL CONSISTENCY of the instrument using Cronbach's Alpha and the instrument's TEST-RETEST CORRELATION using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. According to Collins (2007), Cronbach's Alpha is a way of assessing reliability by comparing the amount of shared variance, or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. The table below shows the interpretation of Cronbach's Alpha.

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INTERPRETATION	
Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Acceptable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Questionable
	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

The following are the results of the reliability test.

INTERNAL CONSISTENCY TEST

Cronbach's Alpha

RELIABILITY STATISTICS	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.915	40

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	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
LENP1	139.0667	117.168	.442	.913
LENP2	139.0333	117.551	.419	.914
LENP3	139.3333	116.230	.431	.913
LENP4	139.0667	117.306	.428	.914
LENP5	139.1667	113.385	.610	.911
SENP1	139.1333	115.292	.599	.912
SENP2	139.0000	119.448	.235	.915
SENP3	139.1333	113.223	.630	.911
SENP4	139.0667	113.857	.674	.911
SENP5	139.1333	115.016	.546	.912
PENP1	139.6667	115.816	.334	.915
PENP2	139.7000	118.493	.160	.918
PENP3	139.7333	115.306	.339	.915
PENP4	139.6667	115.609	.304	.916

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EDP4	139.1000	114.300	.713	.911
EDP5	139.1667	116.006	.455	.913
IMOP1	139.0667	118.616	.296	.915
IMOP2	139.1333	118.533	.248	.915
IMOP3	139.1333	114.533	.588	.912
IMOP4	139.2000	114.372	.669	.911
IMOP5	139.1000	114.162	.632	.911
EMOP1	139.1333	118.257	.314	.915
EMOP2	139.1000	116.162	.527	.913
EMOP3	139.2000	116.303	.381	.914
EMOP4	139.3333	116.989	.274	.916
EMOP5	139.0667	114.961	.511	.912
AFP1	139.4000	115.076	.440	.913
AFP2	139.0667	115.168	.645	.911
AFP3	139.1333	116.051	.526	.912
AFP4	139.2000	115.476	.495	.913
AFP5	139.2333	115.702	.539	.912
EXP1	139.1667	118.075	.282	.915
EXP2	139.0333	116.999	.477	.913
EXP3	139.2000	117.545	.370	.914
EXP4	138.9333	119.168	.306	.915
EXP5	139.1000	118.576	.249	.915

Interpretation: $\alpha = .915$ therefore its reliability is interpreted as EXCELLENT where $\alpha \geq 0.9$

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TEST-RETEST CORRELATION

Test of Stability

Pearson Product-Moment
Correlation

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
PRETEST	141.5667	11.98183	30
POSTTEST	142.7667	11.03813	30

Correlations

		PRETEST	POSTTEST
PRETEST	Pearson Correlation	1	-.024
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.901
	N	30	30
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	-.024	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.901	
	N	30	30

The table above shows the result of correlation between the respondents' pretest and post-test responses. With a p value of $-.024$ and an r value of $.901$. This shows that there is a big difference between the responses on the pretest and the post test. This occurs if the respondents of the pretest and posttest are different persons and/or the test itself was different. In addition, different factors may exist i.e., respondents' mood, environmental conditions, time etc.

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ADDENDUM – RELIABILITY TEST RESULT

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Pearson Product-Moment Correlation

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
PRETEST	141.5667	11.98183	30
POSTTEST	144.8667	8.40252	30

Correlations			
		PRETEST	POSTTEST
PRETEST	Pearson Correlation	1	.903**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	.903**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

** .Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above shows the result of correlation between the respondents' pretest and post-test responses. With a p value of 0.903 and an r value of .0000/<0.05. This proves the stability of the test/indicators.

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Appendix D: Letter for Distribution of Questionnaire

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TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
School of Education

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION IV-A CALABARZON
SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF STO. TOMAS CITY

DIVISION LETTER

To : **MYLENE NATIVIDAD**
School Head – Sto. Tomas Senior High School

All Others Concerned

From : OIC-SCHOOLS DIVISION SUPERINTENDENT

Date : January 25, 2024

Attached herewith is a letter request from **Jake R. Roman, Lenard Vien E. Monares, Merry Ann D. Bernardo, Rodel T. Cornejo** and **Sheri Ann M. Lazaro**, researchers taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education in Tanauan City College to conduct data gathering in SDO Sto. Tomas City relative to their research titled “Inclusive Education, Students’ Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School”.

Permission is hereby granted provided that it adheres to the following conditions:

1. Strict observance of DepEd Time-on-Task Policy;
2. Must be in accordance with the Republic Act No. 10173 – Data Privacy Act of 2012;
3. Participation of respondents must be purely voluntary basis.
4. Results of the study must be treated with utmost confidentiality and that this Office will be provided a copy/result of the research.

For your guidance and information.

NEIL G. ANGELES, CESO VI
Assistant Schools Division Superintendent
Officer-In-Charge
Office of the Schools Division Superintendent

Address: Poblacion IV, Sto Tomas City, Batangas
Telephone No.: (043) 702-8674
Email Address: sdo.santotomas@deped.gov.ph
Website: depedstotomascity.com.ph

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Effectivity	Page 1 of 1

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
School of Education

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

February 02, 2024

MYLENE M. NATIVIDAD
Teacher - in - Charge/Head Teacher II
School Head - Sto. Tomas Senior High School

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled **"Inclusive Education, Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of the Selected Senior High School Students at Sto. Tomas Senior High School"**

In this regard, we are seeking your permission to distribute the attached questionnaire to the Grade 11 & Grade 12 Senior High School students. Your permission will be of great contribution to the success of this undertaking. Rest assured that the answers will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

J. Roman
JAKE R. ROMAN

Lenard Vien E. Monares
LENARD VIEN E. MONARES

Merry Ann D. Bernardo
MERRY ANN D. BERNARDO

Rodel T. Cornejo
RODEL T. CORNEJO

Sheri Ann M. Lazaro
SHERI ANN M. LAZARO
Researcher

Noted:

Rojane F. Bernas

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:
Mylene M. Natividad

MYLENE M. NATIVIDAD
Teacher - in - Charge/Head Teacher II
School Head - Sto. Tomas Senior High School

Kindly assist: Wilma Agustin - STEM/ABM Coordinator

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School of Education

Appendix E: Letter for Research Adviser, Grammarian, Statistician Form

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Republic of the Philippines
 Province of Batangas
 CITY OF TANAUAN

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
 TANAUAN:ityofcolo.s

E-mail: tanaucitycollege@gmail.com Tel. No.: (043) 702 – 6979; (043) 706 – 6961; (043) 706 – 3934
 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tanauan-City-College/554034167997845>

**RESEARCH ADVISER'S
 FORM 1A**

Date: September 14, 2021

Program: Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education

Major

Academic Year: 2023 - 2024

Semester: First Semester

This is to attest that I Rojane Bernas LPT, MAED,
Name of Research Study/ Policy Paper /Business Plan/ Capstone Project Adviser
 have agreed and accepted to be the Adviser of the following students: : Bernardo Merry Ann, Monares Lenard Vien, Lazaro Sheri, Roman Jake, Comejo Rodel with the Research Study/ Policy Paper/Business Plan/Capstone Project entitled:

Furthermore, I agree to set the schedule for advising and consultation to help the students and ensure the success of the study/project.

Rojane Bernas LPT, MAED
 Conforms: _____ Date _____

Noted by: _____
SHARA MAY J. LOGAN, LPT, MAED
 Research Professor _____ Date _____

Approved By: _____
DR. JASCelyn N. OLIMPIADA
 Program Head _____ Date _____

Please furnish copy the RDES0 and submit resume of the adviser

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Province of Batangas
CITY OF TANAUAN

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
TANAUAN City of Calas

E-mail: tanauancitycollege@gmail.com Tel. No.: (043) 702 – 6979; (043) 706 – 6961; (043) 706 – 3934
URL: <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tanauan-City-College/554034167997845>

LANGUAGE EDITOR'S FORM 1B

Date: September 14, 2023

Program: Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education

Major

Academic Year: 2023 - 2024

Semester: First Semester

This is to attest that I Marry Queenie G. Agulo LPT, MAED

Name of Research Study/ Policy Paper/ Business Plan/ Capstone Project Language Editor

have agreed and accepted to be the grammarian of the following students: Bernardo Merry Ann, Monares Lenard Vien, Lazaro Sheri, Roman Jake, Cornejo Rodel, with the Research Study/Policy Paper/Business Plan/Capstone Project entitled:

Furthermore, I agree to set the schedule for checking the manuscript to help the students and ensure the success of the study/project.

Marry Queenie G. Agulo LPT, MAED

Conforme:

_____ Date

Noted by:

SHARA MAY J. LOGAN, LPT, MAED

Research Professor

_____ Date

Approved By:

DR. JASCELYNN N. OLIMPIADA

Program Head

_____ Date

Please furnish copy the RDES0 and submit resume of the language editor.

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Province of Batangas
CITY OF TANAUAN

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
TANAUAN Itoyok, Iloilo

E-mail: tanaucitycollege@gmail.com Tel. No.: (043) 702 – 6979; (043) 706 – 6961; (043) 706 – 3934
URL: <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tanauan-City-College/554034167997845>

STATISTICIAN'S FORM 1C

Date: September 14, 2023

Program: Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education

Academic Year: 2023 - 2024

Semester: First Semester

This is to attest that I Rojane Bernas LPT, MAED,

Name of Research Study/ Policy Paper/Business Plan/ Capstone Project Statistician

have agreed and accepted to be the statistician of the following students: Bernardo Merry Ann, Monares Lenard Vien, Lazaro Sheri Ann, Roman Jake, Cornejo Rodel, with the Research/Business Plan/Capstone Project entitled:

Furthermore, I agree to set the schedule to assist the student-researchers to determine appropriate statistical procedures for the analysis of research data and ensure the success of the study/project.

Rojane Bernas LPT, MAED

Conforme:

_____ Date

Noted by:

SHARA MAY J. LOGAN, LPT, MAED

Research Professor

_____ Date

Approved By:

DR. JASCELYNN N. OLIMPIADA

Program Head

_____ Date

Please furnish copy the RDESO and submit resume of the statistician.

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School of Education

Appendix F: Distribution Tables, Computation of Overall Mean

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Table A
Respondents of the Study

Grade Level	Number of Learners
Grade 11	155
Grade 12	156
TOTAL	311

Table B
Interpretation of Mean Ranges

Numerical Value	Mean Ranges	Interpretations
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree

Table 1
Learner's Proficiency Level

Learners Proficiency Level	Frequency	Percentage
79% and below	1	.3%
80 - 84%	30	9.7%
85 - 89%	121	38.8%
90% and above	159	51.1%
TOTAL	311	100%

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Table 2.1
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive in terms of Learning Environment

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. I constantly learn and grow freely with the support of my teachers	3.34	0.58	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers let us participate in every activity to have a deeper understanding of the topic.	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers value and appreciate my ideas in class.	3.33	0.63	Strongly Agree
4. My teacher uses a wide range of strategies in dealing the topics that apply to all kinds of learners.	3.43	0.65	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers treated us equally in the classroom.	3.27	0.81	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 2.2
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive in terms of Social Environment

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. My teachers encourage rapport with all kinds of learners.	3.14	0.67	Agree
2. My teachers assist me in improving my social abilities.	3.15	0.66	Agree
3. My teachers promote a sense of belonging among all students.	3.06	0.76	Agree
4. My teachers create positive interactions with everyone.	3.12	0.75	Agree
5. My teachers treated us equally in the classroom.	3.25	0.64	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.15	0.70	Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

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Table 2.3
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive Education in terms of Physical Environment

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. The ventilation in the classroom gives a conducive environment that is suitable for learning.	3.31	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. The arrangement of the chairs in the classroom is suitable for all kinds of students.	3.33	0.62	Strongly Agree
3. The facilities in the school are accessible for all students, especially for students with physical disabilities	3.37	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. The lighting in the classroom is appropriate and comfortable for the students.	3.31	0.64	Strongly Agree
5. The physical layout of the school promotes equality for all learners.	3.25	0.72	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.31	0.65	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 2.4
Students' Evaluation of Inclusive Education in terms of Ethnic Diversity

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. My teachers value the diverse backgrounds of the students in class.	3.34	0.59	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers recognize the diversity of the student characteristics in a classroom.	3.35	0.68	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers give equal opportunity for the students to use their cultural knowledge in the classroom.	3.33	0.63	Strongly Agree
4. My teachers effectively promote a sense of belonging and acceptance regardless of my ethnic background.	3.43	0.66	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers reduce any discrimination among students.	3.27	0.81	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
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Table 3.1
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
In terms of Intrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. Completing my activities and assignments beforehand helps me feel more in control of my academic workload.	3.33	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. I love doing schoolwork because it gives me a sense of fulfillment.	3.09	0.78	Agree
3. My enjoyment in doing my task motivates me to keep doing my academic responsibility.	3.30	0.67	Strongly Agree
4. The opportunities for creativity and self-expression that are enhance in the classroom give me motivation to learn.	3.38	0.62	Strongly Agree
5. A supportive and encouraging learning environment enhances my innate motivation.	3.42	0.63	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.31	0.67	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 3.2
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
in terms of Extrinsic Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. The presence of tangible rewards, like certificates or prizes, boosts my drive to accomplish academic objectives.	3.32	0.78	Strongly Agree
2. Receiving high grades is a primary motivator for me to study and complete assignments.	3.41	0.72	Strongly Agree
3. The school's rewards system motivates me equally, regardless of my background.	3.27	0.70	Strongly Agree
4. The fear of negative consequences, such us failing grades or disappointing others, motivated me to work harder.	3.24	0.75	Agree
5. The presence of competitive environments significantly influences my motivation to succeed.	3.25	0.76	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.30	0.74	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 3.3
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
in terms of Affective Motivational Aspects

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. I feel sense of belonging within my academic community.	3.28	0.63	Strongly Agree
2. I am motivated to exert the necessary effort to achieve academic success.	3.35	0.65	Strongly Agree
3. I have been driven to do better in my academic performance because my teacher supports me consistently.	3.23	0.69	Agree
4. My teacher recognizes my emotional being.	3.14	0.75	Agree
5. Engaging in collaborative learning enhances my sense of purpose.	3.19	0.68	Agree
Overall Mean	3.24	0.68	Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 3.4
Level of Students' Motivation in Inclusive Education
in terms of Expectancy Theory of Motivation

Indicators	M	SD	VI
I am feeling motivated in an inclusive education setting because...			
1. I have high expectations when I know I do my best in a given task.	3.49	1.87	Strongly Agree
2. My efforts will always result in success in the classroom.	3.19	0.73	Agree
3. My actions will always lead to positive academic outcomes.	3.23	0.71	Agree
4. Doing my academic responsibilities will benefit me in the future.	3.55	0.61	Strongly Agree
5. I will always expect myself to perform well in class.	3.26	0.79	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.35	0.94	Strongly Agree

M – Mean, SD – Standard Deviation, VI – Verbal Interpretation

Table 4.
Significant Relationship between Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Inclusive Education and Students' Academic Performance	0.135	0.018	Reject H ₀	Significant (Very Weak Positive Correlation)

p<0.05=Significant, p>0.05=Not Significant

Table 5.
Significant Relationship Between Students' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Students' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance	0.159	0.005	Reject H ₀	Significant (Very Weak Positive Correlation)

p<0.05=Significant, p>0.05=Not Significant

Table 6.
Significant Relationship Between Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Inclusive Education and Students' Motivation	0.675	<0.01	Reject H ₀	Significant (Strong Positive Correlation)

p<0.05=Significant, p>0.05=Not Significant

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Appendix G: Computation of Significant Relationship

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Computed Table A: Correlation between inclusive education and students' academic performance.

SOP 4

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Inclusive Education	3.2957	.39019	311
Academic Performance	89.2026	3.67916	311

Correlations

		Student Motivation	Academic Performance
Inclusive Education	Pearson Correlation	1	.135*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.018
	N	311	311
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.135*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.018	
	N	311	311

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

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Computed Table B: Correlation between the students' motivation and students' academic performance.

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SOP 5

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Student Motivation	3.3013	.44122	311
Academic Performance	89.2026	3.67916	311

Correlations

		Student Motivation	Academic Performance
Student Motivation	Pearson Correlation	1	.159**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
	N	311	311
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.159**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
	N	311	311

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

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School of Education

Computed Table C: Correlation between the inclusive education and the student's motivation

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SOP 6

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Inclusive Education	3.2957	.39019	311
Student Motivation	3.3013	.44122	311

Correlations

		Inclusive Education	Student Motivation
Inclusive Education	Pearson Correlation	1	.675**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	311	311
Student Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.675**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	311	311

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

School of Education

CURRICULUM VITAE

145

BERNARDO, MERRY ANN D.

483, Bagbag 3, Tanauan City Batangas, 4232

Contact No.: 0991-324-7609

Email Address: bernardomerryann14@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 21 years old
Gender : Female
Date of Birth : August 16, 2002
Place of Birth : Bagbag 3, Tanauan City Batangas
Height : 4'11
Weight : 45 kg
Civil Status : Single
Religion : Roman Catholic
Languages/Dialect Spoken : Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
Tanauan City Batangas
2021-present

Senior High School : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
Tanauan City Batangas
S/Y 2019-2021

Junior High School : **TINURIK NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL**
Tinurik, Tanauan City Batangas
S/Y 2015-2019

Primary School : **LOOC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**
Balete, Batangas
S/Y 2009-2015

Merry Ann D. Bernardo
Applicant Signature

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
School of Education

CURRICULUM VITAE

CORNEJO, RODEL T.

720, Trapiche 03, Tanauan City Batangas, 4232

Contact No.: 09701486946

Email Address: cornejorodel17@gmail.com

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 24 years old
Gender : Male
Date of Birth : April 01, 2000
Place of Birth : Balayan, Batangas
Height : 5'7
Weight : 60 kg
Civil Status : Single
Religion : Roman Catholic
Languages/Dialect Spoken : Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
Tanauan City Batangas
2019-present

Senior High School : **TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE**
Tanauan City Batangas
S/Y 2017-2019

Junior High School : **BALAYAN COLLEGES**
Palikpikan Street, Brgy. 5 Balayan, Batangas
S/Y 2012-2017

Primary School : **BALAYAN EAST CENTRAL SCHOOL**
Paz Street, Balayan, Batangas
S/Y 2006-2012

Rodel Torres Cornejo
Applicant Signature

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

School of Education

CURRICULUM VITAE

147

LAZARO, SHERI ANN M.

200 E Diamond Street, Josefa Village, Sambat,
Tanauan City Batangas, 4232.
Contact No.: 0968-387-2915
Email Address: sherianlazar010@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age	:	24 years old
Gender	:	Female
Date of Birth	:	April 30, 2000
Place of Birth	:	Sambat, Tanauan City Batangas
Height	:	5'7
Weight	:	57 kg
Civil Status	:	Single
Religion	:	Roman Catholic
Languages/Dialect Spoken	:	Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary	:	TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE Tanauan City Batangas 2019-present
Senior High School	:	TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE Tanauan City Batangas S/Y 2017-2019
Junior High School	:	TANAUAN CITY INTEGRATED HIGH SCHOOL Tanauan City Batangas S/Y 2013-2017
Primary School	:	TANAUAN NORTH CENTRAL SCHOOL Tanauan City Batangas S/Y 2007-2013

Sheri Ann M. Lazaro
Applicant Signature

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
School of Education

CURRICULUM VITAE

148

MONARES, LENARD VIEN E.

Brgy. SanTiago Santo Tomas, Batangas, 4234

Contact No.: 0956-584-8005

Email Address: tcc0201.2021@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 22 years old
Gender : Male
Date of Birth : August 09, 2001
Place of Birth : Santiago Sto Tomas Batangas
Height : 170 cm
Weight : 50 kg
Civil Status : Single
Religion : Roman Catholic
Languages/Dialect Spoken : Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
Tanauan City Batangas
2021-present

Senior High School : STO TOMAS SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL
San Miguel Sto Tomas City, Batangas
S/Y 2019-2021

Junior High School : SAN RAFAEL NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
San Rafael Sto Tomas City, Batangas
S/Y 2012-2017

Primary School : SANTIAGO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL
Santiago Sto Tomas City, Batangas
S/Y 2006-2012

Lenard Vien E. Monares
Applicant Signature

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
School of Education

CURRICULUM VITAE

149

ROMAN, JAKE R.

265, Ambulong Tanauan City, Batangas, 4234
Contact No.: 0938-3442-610
Email Address: tcc0282.2019.dim@gmail.com

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Age : 23 years old
Gender : Male
Date of Birth : February 21, 2001
Place of Birth : Tanauan City, Batangas
Height : 5'9
Weight : 72 kg
Civil Status : Single
Religion : Roman Catholic
Languages/Dialect Spoken : Tagalog and English

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Tertiary : TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
Tanauan City Batangas
2019-present

Senior High School : TANAUAN SCHOOL OF FISHERIES
Ambulong Tanauan City Batangas
S/Y 2017-2019

Junior High School : TANAUAN SCHOOL OF FISHERIES
Ambulong, Tanauan City Batangas
S/Y 2013-2017

Primary School : AMBULONG ELEMENTARY SCHOOL
Ambulong, Tanauan City Batangas
S/Y 2007-2013

Jake R. Roman
Applicant Signature